

The Sustainable and TrAnsparent Research data (STAR) study: Final report

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Jess Wheeler ^{2,1†}

¹University of Bristol, ²UK Reproducibility Network

† Correspondence should be addressed to Neil Jacobs; E-mail: neil.jacobs@bristol.ac.uk.

Author contributions

Conceptualization: Neil Jacobs.
Data curation: Pen-Yuan Hsing.
Formal analysis: Lorna Duncan.
Funding acquisition: Neil Jacobs.
Investigation: Pen-Yuan Hsing, Ros Strang, and Lorna Duncan.
Methodology: Pen-Yuan Hsing and Lorna Duncan.
Project administration: Ros Strang and Lorna Duncan.
Supervision: Neil Jacobs.
Validation: Lorna Duncan.
Writing - original draft: Jess Wheeler.
Writing - review & editing: Jess Wheeler, Pen-Yuan Hsing, Lorna Duncan, and Neil Jacobs.

External Review: Liam Bullingham (University of Essex) and Rachel Bruce (UK Research and Innovation)

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Executive summary

This report covers findings from the UKRN-led STAR (Sustainable and Transparent Research Data) project. Project collaborators included 21 diverse UK Higher Education Institutions (UKHEI), geographically spread across English regions and UK devolved nations, varied in their relative funding wealth; and in the nature, focus, and/or breadth of the subjects and disciplines in which their students, teachers, researchers and/or practitioners specialised. Participants included executive and professional services staff with leadership and delivery responsibilities for institutional open research data (ORD) policy and implementation. STAR project collaborators took part in interviews, focus groups, site visits and workshops, that set out to gauge progress and barriers to ORD implementation, since publication of the 2016 Concordat on ORD. Outcomes and co-designed recommendations to support future UKHEI ORD implementation, are reported here.

The STAR project found that since the publication of the Concordat on ORD in 2016, UKHEIs had made significant progress. Participating institutions were actively demonstrating their commitment to a future in which publicly accessible ORD is a routine and normalised output of publicly funded research. ORD specialists had been recruited into open data posts and were champions of institutional ORD implementation, often the authors of institutional ORD policy and guidance. ORD policy and guidance was mostly available to academic communities in visible and accessible formats. Dedicated institutional ORD repositories were in place and ORD workers provided expert assistance to support effective data preparation and appropriate use of ORD repositories. ORD support included detailed data scrutiny, curation and training in the standards and skills required to promote FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) standards of open data publication. Training in ORD processes and standards was regularly offered to postgraduates and also to established research and teaching staff and postgraduate supervisors. There were many and varied examples of research data that had been successfully openly published and stored within institutional repositories.

Despite these strong indicators of increasingly established ORD policy and infrastructure, it was evident that making research data open remained a relatively small-scale and exceptional, rather than routine and ubiquitous, activity among institutional research communities. In general, it appeared that a majority of research communities remained unfamiliar with repository technologies, open data curation standards and practices, ORD publication and reuse. Apart from those mandated as part of postgraduate courses, academic staff did not readily take up the ORD training that was increasingly on offer to them. It appeared that for the most part, when researchers sought to openly publish data, this was to satisfy stringent journal publication requirements, rather than institutional ORD policy or guidance, which was readily ignored.

There were multiple, simultaneously operating barriers to uptake of ORD activities. Inclusivity was a recurrent issue. Academic communities with divergent disciplinary practices, outputs, and epistemic values, did not always identify their work as 'data', or even necessarily as 'research'. Similarly, the presumed value of ORD as a public good, makes sense in the context of tangible anticipated positive impacts (e.g. generative plans for open data reuse). For work with less obvious reuse potential, any inherent justification for spending time, effort and costs on ORD activities, remained weak.

Even among research communities able to share in a unified ORD vision, or who recognise an inherent value in making data open, because of obvious reuse potential, many were not yet fully prepared to take on ORD work within their funded projects. They lacked data curation skills and were unlikely to have allocated sufficient time or costs to ORD activities. Researchers and the finance teams who approved their project costs and budgets, did not yet routinely or effectively recognise costs associated with ORD practices within funding applications. ORD workers had also not yet established systems to efficiently monitor a plurality of ORD databases, to capture and evaluate their research communities' ORD outputs and impacts. As a result, ORD work lacked the visibility of regular reporting, and neither the

threat of compliance checks nor the promise of recognition and reward served to incentivise ORD practices. In this context ORD work remained irregular, mostly invisible labour. Given the additional impact of funder, institutional, departmental and project financial pressures, ORD was unlikely to be routinely prioritised.

To compensate, ORD workers, typically enthusiastic proponents of ORD, described spending considerable time on the 'translation work' of inclusion, attempting to expand the concept of 'open research data', to accommodate the work and interests of their varied academic communities. ORD workers also described providing detailed data curation assistance to promote effective ORD publication among inexperienced academic staff. As a result, ORD workers and teams, typically a relatively small and finite presence within their institutions, were often working at capacity, despite serving relatively small proportions of their overall academic communities. It was widely recognised that it would not be possible to scale up ORD activities, to include entire institutional research communities, on the basis of the current intensity of dedicated specialist ORD assistance. It was clear that open research data workers and teams needed their academic colleagues of all disciplines to get more solidly and autonomously on board with the vision and values of ORD implementation and the skilled work of data stewardship. In this vein, they offered regular training and published accessible open research data curation and repository-use guidance.

However, the push for academic communities to take on this work, appeared muted. Despite notable progress, there was a sense of stasis and cautious anticipation. In the context of strongly perceived financial, workload and staff capacity pressures, most felt an external pressure (e.g. funder compliance checks, or more stringent ORD REF requirements) would be needed, for institutions to risk diverting additional resources to scale-up ORD implementation. As such, open research data implementation appeared to have hit a glass ceiling. Institutions and dedicated ORD staff continued to work hard, but were already over-stretched in their efforts. The journey towards ubiquitous open research data publication appeared to have reached a point where open research data publication was encouraged, was possible, and where standards of excellence were promoted, generating prominent examples of best practice. There was little sign of institutional or research community push, beyond this early emergent phase, to make open research data activities routine and normalised practice.

Co-developed recommendations began with the need to **increase the inclusiveness of the language and examples of ORD**, to better connect with disciplinarily diverse researcher communities to the work of ORD, including implementation decision making processes. Core to all further recommendations, was the need to **reconnect ORD values to ORD work**, outputs and anticipated impacts, as a balanced moral and pragmatic concern for each research project. To support this, we recommend the establishment of **formalised institutional or departmental processes of ORD review** as an addition to current ethical review processes or as part of data management planning or, ideally, as an integrated process. Formal ORD review processes would allow researchers to strengthen and better formulate their ORD outputs, by setting out and justifying the time, skilled labour and costs involved in generating ORD outputs, and any additional work required to connect proposed ORD outputs to relevant audiences beyond their proximate research community and to increase opportunities for anticipated scrutiny and impact. This process of review would allow projects to better specify, justify and account for ORD costs in their project budgets, removing the invisibility of ORD labour and better connecting research communities to the inherent value of ORD outputs in relation to their own work. This would also allow projects where justification for ORD outputs remained weak, and other research priorities and impacts were better supported, to avoid ORD work, costs and outputs, through formal exemption, allowing research time, costs and efforts to be focused more appropriately on other areas. This would move us beyond the current, generalised, future-oriented approach to ORD, that treats all research as of equal ORD value, and requires all researchers to produce ORD, not because this is justified in relation to their particular program of work, but as a contribution to a future

in which ORD is a routine, normalised output. This future framing may be necessary at the early emergent phase of ORD implementation, but is seen to in the long run to alienate researchers, ignoring moral and pragmatic concerns, that will continue to lead researchers, who face multiple pressures on limited project resources to continue to avoid ORD activities, but at increasing risk of reputational damage (both their own and their institutions). Better formulating institutional processes of ORD review that connect the value of ORD outputs to the relative costs, and support formal exemptions where appropriate, would allow researchers to consider these values more carefully, and to account for the work of ORD more effectively, connecting proposed time, work and costs to specific outputs and impacts. This would be less alienating and would also support engagement from currently disengaged research communities, for whom the relevance of engagement with formal review processes, would be clear, especially if these review processes were linked to compliance, monitoring and evaluation processes, and would ensure that those with formal justification for exemption from ORD outputs would not be penalised for failure to generate ORD.

The ability to cost, describe and assess impacts, that would inform formal ORD review, provides a backbone for the implementation of compliance and evaluation processes, while protecting those currently in need of exemptions, but creating a framework for their future engagement, given changing costs, skills, and reuse possibilities.

Other recommendations are proposed that address the perceived disconnects between ORD requirements, ORD specialist work and many research communities in terms of values, as well as pragmatic and technical concerns. Implementation of these recommendations would complement the adoption of the institutional review processes noted above.

1. Introduction

“...an interactive sea of shared knowledge” Tim Berners-Lee, 1995 (1)

The potential for data to be stored in accessible digital formats and globally shared, has never been greater. Today, we can imagine ever expanding, faster and more efficient advances in science, technology and innovation(2); greater freedom and equity of access to research outputs; and increased democratisation of the processes of enquiry that shape human knowledge and development (3). All of these are apt ambitions for publicly-funded research. In this context, data accessibility and reuse has a significant part to play in shaping our future – and as we move into the data-hungry era of AI information processing, perhaps never more so (4).

Our report focuses on progress in one aspect of the data landscape; open research data (ORD). A recent UNESCO definition is helpful (5):

“Open research data: that include, among others, digital and analogue data, both raw and processed, and the accompanying metadata, as well as numerical scores, textual records, images and sounds, protocols, analysis code and workflows that can be openly used, reused, retained and redistributed by anyone, subject to acknowledgement... available in a timely and user-friendly, human- and machine- readable and actionable format, in accordance with principles of good data governance and stewardship, notably the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles, supported by regular curation and maintenance.”

UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science, 2021 (5)

For this report, we have worked together with executive leaders and ORD specialists from a wide range of UK Higher Education Institutions (UKHEIs), to investigate progress and sustainability in the policies, infrastructures and practices that are making ORD possible and the barriers that impede progress. Through in-depth interviews, focus groups and site visits we have explored in some granular detail ORD policy and implementation within research institutions.

Together with our UKHEI participants we have used our findings to co-develop a series of recommendations to support UKHEIs in their onwards ORD journeys. Some recommendations relate directly to the work of UKHEIs and associated research communities. Others relate more broadly to the work of UK Research and Innovation (UKRI), UK research councils, as well as other funders, publishers, data repository and registration services that support ORD work, all of which play their own vital parts in shaping the UK (and global) ORD ecosystem.

1.1 The Concordat on Open Research Data

This study builds on the work of the ‘Concordat on Open Research Data’ (referred to from here as ‘the Concordat on ORD’), launched in 2016 by Universities UK, Wellcome, the Higher Education Funding Council for England (HEFCE, now UK Research and Innovation - UKRI), and the UK Research Councils (6). The Concordat on ORD made the case that, given increasingly available ORD-enabling technologies, publicly-funded research should, in all but exceptional cases, be openly publicly accessible. Openness was presented as a key driver of greater research scrutiny, integrity, quality, efficiency and advance; increased public engagement, trust in, and support for research; leading to greater knowledge, wisdom,

economic growth and development (3). To support this progress, the Concordat on ORD set out a series of principles to guide the development of ORD within UK HEIs.

1.2. A brief history of UK ORD policy development

A series of landmark historical developments paved the way to the Concordat on ORD in the UK (7). In 2007, the 30 member countries of the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) produced the 'Principles and Guidelines for Access to Research Data from Public Funding' (8). This report championed ORD as a public good, and targeted OECD-member governments' science policies and funding bodies, aiming to stimulate national strategies, policies, guidance and funding relevant to progress in ORD.

In the UK, the then Research Councils UK (RCUK) responded with a series of codes of practice for research, principles and guidance for good research conduct, spanning from the 2008 'Expectations for Societal and Economic Impact' to the 2015 'Guidance on Good Practice in the Management of Research Data'. The UK Research Integrity Office (UKRIO) responded similarly, with its 2009 Code of Practice for Research (9). In 2012, the Royal Society published the 'Science as an open enterprise' report (10). These reports, policies, codes and guidelines laid the ground for the cross-sector consultations that underpinned the 2016 Concordat on ORD.

1.3. Compliance-driven approaches

The Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC) produced its own policy framework on research data in 2011 (11) and took a relatively firm approach. Research organisations were required to specify and initiate processes for the implementation of ORD policies, to bring in infrastructure and to educate researchers. The EPSRC set deadlines and linked compliance to funding. This move was a significant driver of UK higher education institutes (HEIs) ORD policy and infrastructure development in the early 2010s, in particular for those with significant EPSRC funding interests. However, this approach also exposed tensions among research communities. ORD directives in some disciplines, outpaced opportunities to shape the desired processes among research communities with different ontological and epistemological values and foundations. This situation was perhaps not helped by decisions such as that to close the Arts and Humanities Data Service in 2008.

1.4. Disciplinary differences and readiness

The challenges posed by disciplinary diversity to UK institutional ORD implementation are worth noting. For some researchers, especially those in lab-based, electronic-data heavy, experimental Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) research communities, progress in the availability and accessibility of ORD was, by 2007, already advanced. To put this in perspective, by 2008, 'GenBank' the United States National Institute for Health-funded, free-of-charge and publicly available, nucleic acid sequence databank, had been operating for over a quarter of a century, as had its European competitor, EMBL. Mechanisms for authorship, proprietary interests, distribution, and publication had been fought, negotiated, hard won and delicately resolved, back in the 1980s (12-14).

Among research communities for whom digitised data was already a natural output; for those steeped in positivist philosophies of observation and experimentation, for whom reproducibility and correction are core components of validation; and among those with foundational histories of preservation, classification and collaboration – for all these kinds of research disciplines, strengthening local and global ORD availability, widening accessibility and increasing reuse makes obvious sense for the advance of scientific knowledge. Indeed, for researchers well used to preserving and sharing their findings through mature international open data repository

infrastructures, already part of rapidly advancing, richly-collaborative disciplinary communities (e.g. particle physics, astrophysics, genetics, biotechnology), the adoption and implementation of ORD policy within UKHEIs in the 2010s may well have seemed snail-paced and somewhat irrelevant to rapid and internationally-connected ORD developments within their own fields.

Yet for other research communities, institutional emphasis on ORD in recent years may have seemed irrelevant for entirely different reasons. This list includes: researchers who do not naturally view their work as 'science'; those steeped in interpretivist epistemologies; those whose work centres on embodied, tangible, multi-sensory outputs; those for whom 'digitised data' is not an obvious, necessary, or natural output; those for whom novel creation, insight and inspiration might be characterised by insular and idiosyncratic reflection, rather than collaboration and data availability; those whose sources are in archives, museums or libraries, and; those for whom 'research data' might mean a life's work of laboriously collected, carefully protected, confidential, sensitive, reflexively-understood, researcher-contingent, personal accounts and observations. For these diverse creators and researchers - more typically based in arts and humanities disciplines - the value and relevance of ORD could be far from self-evident (15-18).

While all the RCUK research councils committed to the same ORD principles, requirements for implementation varied. Details varied; not all research councils chose to adopt compliance-driven approaches, meaning compliance requirements for ORD varied across disciplines and in relation to major funders. Different research communities had different policy, infrastructure and guidance needs. In response, RCUK produced the 2011 'Common Principles on Data Policy' offering an overarching framework that disparate disciplinary data policies could sit more comfortably within, steering towards openness, while leaving space for a multiplicity of differently paced responses to implementation.

1.5. Ethical, proprietary and commercial concerns

It was evident from the outset that ethical and commercial policies could stymie ORD progress, and needed to be understood and addressed. Ethical policies and guidance for the protection of sensitive human data needed to develop processes of consent and ethical review that could appropriately enable, but where necessary restrict, sharing and reuse of deidentified human data (19, 20).

Any sense that ORD policy might threaten the protection of commercially-sensitive, privately-funded, and costly research outputs, and by association innovation, needed to be clarified to recognise commercial interests, partnerships and investments. This recognition also needed to be balanced with an understanding that commercialisation and ORD need not always be mutually exclusive. Similarly, developments in ORD needed to ensure strong recognition, acknowledgement and credit for researcher's innovation, insight, effort, and creation, and to clearly address issues of intellectual property (21).

1.6. Practical challenges and the need to be 'FAIR'

There were many practical challenges to consider, related to the infrastructures, technologies, databases and data curation skills needed to effectively deliver ORD. The FAIR Principles, also published in 2016 (22), set out core standards needed to attain ORD accessibility and re-usability. For ORD to be FAIR, it has to be: Findable (using rich and coherent metadata, that is both machine and human readable); Accessible (it must be readily accessible through fair and inclusive processes of authentication and authorisation); Interoperable (usable by different users, for different purposes, and with different kinds of data operating systems); Reusable (well-described, replicable, available in formats and with licences that enable

reanalysis and combination with other data). Since their inception, the FAIR Principles have been widely embraced .

To achieve FAIR standards, in a disciplinarily diverse and multiple repository environment, operating across globally-located research institutions and communities, requires considerable data management and technological alignment, collaboration, agreement, adaptation and development. This work relates to a broad and burgeoning ORD ecosystem, an international array of repository and technology service providers, research oversight bodies, research institutions, data curation specialists, and research communities. To realise the core value of 'public access to publicly funded research', FAIR principles need also to be inclusive of 'citizen researchers' - and ORD system development to be mindful of access and usability concerns relevant to a wide global public.

In recognition of these challenges, there was acceptance that infrastructure costs and challenges needed to be appreciated, and time allowed to build appropriate data services, and to support ORD professional skills development among data specialists and researchers.

Despite the clarity of FAIR principles, the requisite structure and oversight of data systems remained unclear. For instance, should ORD repositories be held and served institutionally, versus nationally or as part of disciplinary-specific national or international-collaborative structures? Oversight, transparency and monitoring issues and questions about the right mix, kinds and governance of publicly-owned/funded, versus privately-owned/funded, commercial or non-commercial data service providers, all needed time to percolate and to be resolved.

1.7. Financial challenges

A final but important contextual issue relates to both national and UK HEI financial circumstances (23). In 2007 the OECD science ministers presented their 'Principles and Guidelines for Access to Research Data from Public Funding', championing ORD as a public good that required active and intensive development. By 2008 the global financial crisis had created the deepest UK recession since the second world war. Since 2008, UK annual economic growth has, on average, flat-lined. The financing of research, research institutions, and the progress of open research, along with other public goods, has inevitably been shaped by the rocky financial climate that followed the 2008 financial crisis and ensuing recession. In 2016 (the year of the Concordat on ORD), the UK voted to leave the European Union (EU), resulting in economic insecurity and with distinct negative repercussions for UK research collaborations, access to EU research funding and HEI research and financial security (24-27). More recently, there has been progress in negotiations to enable easier European research collaborations and UK access to EU research funding opportunities (28). However, long-term financial restrictions - linked to national economic and political factors, international and geopolitical circumstances, a global pandemic, UK financial austerity, inflation, real-term cuts in domestic student fees, and shifting international student flows, alongside institutional over-reliance on overseas student fees - have resulted in UK institutions experiencing extremely tough financial circumstances (23, 29). Despite headline figures indicating growth in UK public R+D spend, HEI-sector financial pressures create an uncomfortable backdrop to the present report.

1.8. The Principles

The Concordat on ORD was developed in 2016, pre Brexit, but with awareness of the challenges that UK HEIs faced in relation to ORD progress. A series of cross-sector working groups considered proposals drawn from the evolving array of RCUK principles, guidance and codes. The Concordat on ORD that emerged, strongly promoted the effort to make research data open, wherever and as much as possible, as a public good. It reflected the widely

recognised challenges and tensions at play (as set out, 1.3 to 1.6, above), including ethical and commercial sensitivities, concerns for intellectual property, credit, appropriate data curation, and the costs and time involved in infrastructure development. It set out ten guiding principles, summarised below:

- Principle #1:** *Open access to research data is an enabler of high quality research, a facilitator of innovation and safeguards good research practice.*
- Principle #2:** *There are sound reasons why the openness of research data may need to be restricted but any restrictions must be justified and justifiable.*
- Principle #3:** *Open access to research data carries a significant cost, which should be respected by all parties.*
- Principle #4:** *The right of the creators of research data to reasonable first use is recognised.*
- Principle #5:** *Use of others' data should always conform to legal, ethical and regulatory frameworks including appropriate acknowledgement.*
- Principle #6:** *Good data management is fundamental to all stages of the research process and should be established at the outset.*
- Principle #7:** *Data curation is vital to make data useful for others and for long-term preservation of data.*
- Principle #8:** *Data supporting publications should be accessible by the publication date and should be in a citeable form.*
- Principle #9:** *Support for the development of appropriate data skills is recognised as a responsibility for all stakeholders.*
- Principle #10:** *Regular reviews of progress towards open research data should be undertaken.*

The principles of the Concordat on ORD set out to be comprehensive and actionable, promoting open research, but also supportive of transparently justified exceptions; urging for all research data to be 'as open as possible, as closed as necessary'. This (now familiar) mantra set the intention for openness to become the norm, while accepting justified deviations due to 'relevant legal, ethical, disciplinary and regulatory frameworks...and with due regard to the costs involved'.(30)

Universities UK (UUK), a membership organisation representing the interests of many UKHEIs, signed the Concordat on ORD in 2016, endorsing compliance with its principles and expectations of good practice. However, adoption and adherence were not assumed or required of UUK members.

1.9. Progress since 2016

Since the Concordat on ORD, there have been several international developments that are relevant to the current study. Of these, two perhaps warrant particular note. The first is the drafting of the CARE Principles for indigenous data governance (52). While explicitly focused on data sovereignty and related matters for indigenous people, the Principles have wider applicability where ethical questions arise in the use of culturally, socially or economically significant data for research purposes. The second, already cited above, is the 2021 UNESCO Recommendation on Open Science (UNESCO, 2021), which imposes expectations onto member states with respect to, among other things, ORD and related infrastructure.

Specifically looking at the UK, some major projects have been undertaken, which inform this report and have contributed to our understanding of progress and barriers in relation to UK ORD policy goals, and UKHEIs ORD progress more specifically.

1.9.1. Open Research Data Task Force

In 2016, the UK Government Department of Science, Innovation and Technology set up an Open Research Data Task Force, to lead on creating a 'roadmap' for ORD, to support co-ordinated action, and to manage the combined risks of a fragmented ecosystem and uneven expertise in ORD issues. The ORD Task Force reported its recommendations in 2018 (31, 32), highlighting the need to:

- **improve incentives**
Including funder and publisher support and encouragement of ORD citations and data reuse; institutional recognition of ORD achievements in promotion criteria; the development of REF criteria for ORD.
- **reduce barriers**
Including development of data repository infrastructures, specialist ORD support, funded training and skills development for researchers.
- **provide active leadership**
UKRI to coordinate those with relevant interests, to ascertain roles, responsibilities and distribution of resources within the UK and international ORD ecosystem, to ensure coherence, while respecting disciplinary diversity, to take stock of alternative approaches, such as the Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur, or [NFDI](#), in Germany and outcomes(33).
- **clarify expectations**
Research organisations, funders, research councils to offer clear guidance on:
 - which data or research components to preserve and how to decide;
 - which repositories to use and when;
 - transparency, including data access statements and open access data linked to research publications;
 - sector-wide policy commitments (e.g. the Concordat on ORD and FAIR principles);
 - expectations related to intellectual property rights;
 - the formal role of ORD in relation to research integrity, impact, knowledge exchange;
 - appropriate research metrics to capture ORD work and contributions;
 - clear and formal requirements for ORD relevant to data management plans, research governance, monitoring, review and evaluation.
- **user-friendly services**
Research organisations and funders to ensure that, across all subjects and disciplines, researchers as both creators and users of data have access to user-friendly and appropriate ORD services:
 - Jisc to lead on the development of principles for negotiation with commercial ORD platform providers;
 - funders and research organisations to focus on developing sustainable ORD infrastructure;

- UKRI to lead in the development of a roadmap for UK ORD, working with all relevant organisations and interest groups relevant to ORD policy, technical developments, standards, software, taxonomies and infrastructures.
- **sustainable funding**

National review of costs, business and funding models for UK data services, with consideration of both sustainability and potential for development;

 - funders require currently funded data services to develop their plans for ORD;
 - review of research organisations ORD infrastructure and support provision to ensure sufficient funding to meet future needs;
 - fund new initiatives, including ‘challenge funds’ to target gaps in provision to make ORD readily usable and to support national research priorities, and wider public concerns.

The ORD Taskforce report also recognised the need for engagement work, to understand the concerns of disciplinarily diverse research communities (within the UKRI, HEIs, other research organisations, funders and service providers). The report recognised that the rallying call for progress on ORD, needed to be tempered by deep understanding, respect for and sensitivity to different research practices, cultures and needs. Consultation and engagement work also needed to take in wider public interests in ORD and associated public accessibility issues.

1.9.2. UUK, Wellcome and UKRI Concordats and Agreements review

Universities UK, Wellcome and UKRI commissioned two projects to investigate the role of 12 sector concordats and similar agreements, including the Concordat on ORD, in supporting effective research culture and working environments in the UK. In the first project (34), 510 staff (with oversight or implementation roles) were surveyed at 81 organisations (HEIs or Research Institutes). Respondents generally viewed the initiatives (including the Concordat on ORD) as having positive impacts, but in general had concerns about the burdens of implementation and the need to look beyond individual policies, to broader, intersectional issues. A quarter of respondents indicated that the Concordat on ORD had been adopted by their institution. The second project (35) recommended the adoption of a set of values and principles to underpin efforts to simplify bureaucracy and render sector expectations on research environments. Of relevance to the current study, the principles included that research environments should be inclusive, efficient and situated.

1.9.3. The ‘State of Open Data’ global survey

The State of Open Data survey has reported annually since 2016(36). This survey is the result of a collaboration between [Digital Science](#), [Figshare](#), [Springer Nature](#) (UK-based research publishing /open data service providers with global reach). The survey attempts to capture views and perceptions of ORD among a global research community, and in 2024 made use of available ORD metadata, including Springer Nature journal publication data availability statements (DAS), Digital Science’s [Dimensions.ai](#) research information database, and the [Datacite](#) and [Make Data Count Data Citation Corpus](#) (MDC DCC, funded by [Wellcome](#)). The 2024 report cross referenced outputs and assessed the quantity and kinds of DAS researchers were providing in publications, tracking emerging trends in the link between published research and ORD.

The State of Open Data survey provides a global overview, but some findings relate specifically to UK HEI ORD progress. Relative to other countries, major UK funders were noted

to offer clearer ORD policy frameworks and mandates. UK research scored above average in linking ORD to publications. UK researchers reported the highest awareness of the FAIR principles among the globally surveyed researchers. It was noted that the 2021 UK National Data Strategy (37) emphasised the importance of open data and that there has been significant investment in infrastructure to promote data sharing and stewardship. Two of the universities with the highest global levels of publications linked to accessible data (through the MDC DCC or Dimensions.ai) were UK HEIs (University of Oxford and UCL).

Relative UK strengths were set against a global context of increasingly prevalent DAS within research publications, but slow growth in ORD availability. The US, Germany, UK and France were all found to be 'clustering around 25%' for published research linked to open data repositories. In addition, great unevenness was recognised between disciplines in ORD availability. In relation to UKHEIs, the report makes the case that research institutions with stronger ORD infrastructures and support services have greater potential to drive forward implementation of government and funder policy. It also noted that funder mandates and monitoring of ORD delivery/compliance, as well as academic recognition for ORD and data reuse, remain key areas for progress.

1.10. The Research Excellence Framework (REF)

The REF - the UK system for assessing excellence in research in UK HEIs, that informs the allocation of £2billion public funding - wields considerable power, shaping research strategy, policy and implementation within UKHEIs. In contrast to concrete criteria and strong mandates related to open access publications, ORD has featured relatively lightly in REF criteria and guidance. While the aim for all public-funded research to be made open has been clearly stated, there has not been an equally clear mandate for implementation. The need to allow time for infrastructure development has instead been acknowledged. In 2021, progress on the principles of the Concordat on ORD was mentioned as a 'potential indicator' that institutions could cite in their environment statement. The 2029 guidance is yet to be fully fleshed out, but initial documentation suggests support for ORD will remain reticent, as part of Strategy, People and Research Environment, likely with greater reference to key 'indicators' of implementation, including FAIR principles. One of the aims of the present report is to support the evolution of this guidance in the context of a continuing focus on reducing research bureaucracy.

1.11. UKRI ORD policy and investment

At the time of this study, a new integrated UKRI research data policy was being developed to update the approaches of the Research Councils' noted in sections 1.2-1.3 above. Furthermore, UKRI invests in digital research infrastructure, for example, the Digital Research Infrastructure (DRI) Programme "funds research and innovation in data and computing systems. It supports people and organisations developing the tools, services and skills that strengthen the UK's digital research infrastructure" (53). Such investment includes services and professional development that support ORD.

1.12. UK open access publication roll-out

In contrast to ORD, sector-wide movement on policy, funding and governance to support UK open access publication, happened both more forcefully and more rapidly. Different barriers were at play; as the internet matured in the early 2000s, publications were already increasingly available in electronic online versions, with new 'open access' publication models emerging, but still many reputable and established journals were hidden behind paywalls, curtailing access. The research community broadly supported wider access for their publications; the digital infrastructure was available; barriers related more to publishing interests and business

models, and the need to unlock alternative models of publication funding, to move beyond established journal subscription access constraints (39-42), at least in the Global North.

The 2012 Finch report (50) was a decisive moment for UK open access policy and implementation; making strident recommendations which were uniformly adopted by UK government policymakers, research councils, and funders alike. By 2021, the REF required all submitted journal publications to be available in open access formats, providing a hefty steer towards open access publication for researchers based in UK HEIs. The Finch Report viewed ORD as a paired concern, stemming from the same moral imperative; to make all publicly-funded research outputs openly available and accessible for the widest possible interrogation and reuse. However, ORD infrastructure development was recognised as a more complex undertaking, requiring a longer lead-in time.

UK HEI open access implementation remains recent within the collective memories of the UK HEI research communities, librarians and data teams. It demonstrated that open research landscapes can shift rapidly and dramatically, given available technologies and unified directives, especially where significant status and funding consequences are attached to non-compliance. However, the open access story serves partly as a warning - REF directives can be blunt instruments. Rapid progress in open access publication also brought unintended consequences (40, 43, 44). The REF is recognised as a powerful tool, able to instigate rapid change - but also a danger, with the potential for unforeseen impacts that need to be carefully considered. Disciplinary sensitivities around ORD, coupled with additional workload and cost concerns, suggest the need for continued caution. It was partly these considerations that led UKRN partner institutions in 2024 to set up the STAR study.

1.13. Sustainable and Transparent Research Data Study (STAR)

The STAR study set out to explore implementation of the Concordat on ORD in the 8 years since its publication, through in-depth investigation of its adoption at a diverse range of UK HEIs, including large and small institutions, both disciplinarily niche and broad-ranging research communities, spanning across the devolved nations and UK regions, and regardless of whether or not HEIs had explicitly endorsed or adopted the Concordat on ORD or affiliated with the UKRN.

The study aimed to understand how the principles of the Concordat on ORD have been interpreted and met, with what levels of sustainability, and to describe the barriers and opportunities at play. The study sought to gather evidence through reviews of policies and procedures, in-depth staff interviews, focus groups and site visits involving diverse HEI workers. It aimed to work with participants to co-develop guidance for use across the sector and to support national policy and strategy development.

2. Aims and objectives

The STAR study aimed to understand progress in the implementation of the Concordat on ORD in UKHEIs.

Specific objectives were to:

- 1) derive a set of implementation tasks from the principles in the Concordat on ORD that make implied HEI responsibilities explicit;
- 2) collect available institutional policy and other documentation from UKRN member HEIs and other HEIs participating in the study, to identify progress on and approaches to implementation of the principles of the Concordat on ORD, linking these to identified implementation tasks (1), interview and focus group findings (3);
- 3) assess through interviews, focus groups and case study site visits, the extent and ways in which a diverse sample of UK HEIs have implemented the principles of the Concordat on ORD; exploring any barriers to, and benefits of, this implementation, as well as the sustainability of progress of achievements;
- 4) co-produce and disseminate practical guidance to support the development of sustainable arrangements for ORD practices by UK HEI institutions, and document insights for research funders and research data service providers to inform their work and policies.

3. Methods

STAR was a collaborative study, co-funded and co-designed with UK HEI partners, using co-production methods for the generation of outputs. Research partners, and UK HEI interview, site visit and focus group participants were from a diverse spectrum of UK HEIs (some affiliated with UKRN, some not). At the request of partners and participants, co-production workshops included contributors from the wider ORD ecosystem (e.g. research funders, research councils, data service providers, including: the [Digital Curation Centre](#) (DCC), [UKRI](#), [Wellcome](#), [GuildHE](#), [Fairsharing.org](#)).

In line with objectives, the study involved four areas of research activity, described in 3.1 – 3.4 below.

3.1. ORD implementation tasks

To evaluate progress on ORD, concrete implementation tasks were described for each of the Concordat on ORD's principles. This preliminary work was undertaken by staff at the DCC in collaboration with sector experts and the UKRN-led STAR study research team. The pilot phase (conducted in spring 2023) ascribed 16 tasks to the ten principles (45).

The identified implementation tasks were used to support HEI policy review and were shared with participants and discussed during interviews. Implementation tasks were used to help establish concrete signs of ORD progress. The tasks were also assessed for their usefulness as markers of tangible and sustainable progress within diverse UK HEI research environments.

3.2. HEI documentation related to implementation of the Concordat on ORD

Public-facing policy and other publicly available or sharable documentation related to implementation of the Concordat on ORD (e.g. repository guidance or training provision) was obtained in electronic formats through direct communication (e.g. emails preceding/following interviews) with HEI study participants, also from HEI participant websites, or via Fairsharing.org. Those taking part in interviews were asked to provide relevant documentation that was sharable and/or already publicly available.

Alongside participating HEI ORD policies, REF5a environment statements were collected. REF5a statements were prepared for the 2021 REF submission to describe an HEI's context and mission; strategy, people and income; infrastructure and facilities (46). As outlined (1.10), implementation of the Concordat on ORD was noted in REF 2021 guidance as potential evidence of a positive research environment. A review of REF5a statements was used to develop a series of well-defined, ascertainable 'implementation tasks', that mapped onto the principles of the Concordat on ORD. This work included REF5a statements from 30 UKRN affiliated HEIs (3.1).

Policy documents were reviewed to establish diversity and commonality across HEIs in their approaches to implementing ORD goals, and in relation to the principles of the Concordat on ORD. Policy documentation was cross-referenced with and linked to interview and focus group data (3.3).

3.3. Interviews, focus groups, site visits

In-depth semi-structured interviews and focus groups with professional staff from a diverse selection of UK HEIs, set out to gain an understanding of ORD progress and Concordat implementation from those with direct involvement in, and oversight of, ORD implementation

processes. Site visits sought to bring additional insight through observation of HEI committees or meetings with an ORD focus.

3.3.1. Selection of HEIs

HEIs were selected to include a diverse range of institutions by size, discipline and geography. Eligible UK HEIs were all those that made submissions to REF2021. All eligible UK HEIs were categorised and ranked, creating a sampling matrix, that reflected:

- research intensity - as determined by the amount of QR funding each HEI received;
- research focus – subject areas, using the ‘Unit of Assessment’ subjects submitted to REF21 (46)
- geographical region in the UK

HEIs were selected from across the sampling matrix to capture a breadth of perspectives in relation to research intensity; research focus (ensuring inclusion of HEIs across a broad range of disciplinary perspectives and concerns, as well as HEIs with greater breadth versus specificity of disciplinary range and focus); and to sample HEIs across the devolved nations and across broad geographic regions of the UK (see Table 1 below).

3.3.2 Selection of professional staff

Professional staff from selected HEIs were approached, seeking out those with ORD roles, involved in implementation of the Concordat on ORD or involved in other ways with institutional ORD development (directors, managers, workers and ORD leads within library services, and/or from other areas of professional and technical services linked to ORD implementation, and/or those with senior executive roles involved in the development or implementation and oversight of ORD strategy e.g. Pro-Vice Chancellor for Research and Innovation, and/or researchers with involvement in institutional ORD decision-making processes).

For HEIs who were UKRN members, UKRN leads were approached to help find relevant contacts and to support introductions. For HEIs who were not UKRN members, appropriate ORD leads were identified via study partner contacts, websites, representative bodies (e.g. GuildHE), or during early stages of the research (3.1 and 3.2). Whether UKRN affiliated or not, relevant staff members from selected institutions were approached by email to discuss their participation, and/or to identify others, using a snowballing strategy to reach participants with relevant ORD roles within HEIs.

Where no staff members from a selected HEI were available or responsive to approaches within the study timeframe, another HEI with similar characteristics was selected from the sampling matrix.

Representative organisations approached to support engagement with the study included: [GuildHE](#), the Society of College, National and University Libraries ([SCONUL](#)), the Association of Research Managers and Administrators ([ARMA](#)) and Universities UK ([UUK](#)).

3.3.3. Interviews/ focus groups methods

Informed consent was obtained from relevant professional staff for interviews and focus groups to be audio-recorded in appropriate securely stored formats. Semi-structured interviews/ focus groups could be undertaken remotely or in-person. Additional requests were made for access to policy and other relevant shareable documentation related to ORD while arranging interviews. A topic guide was developed and tested with the support of the wider study team, that covered:

- a) perspectives on the Concordat on ORD and the institution's relationship to it;
- b) how/ whether the ten principles of the Concordat on ORD (and/ or their derived tasks) had been implemented by the HEI (alongside review of relevant documentation obtained);
- c) people within the HEI involved in implementation of the Concordat on ORD;
- d) implementation issues e.g. barriers facing different staff members - researchers, professional and technical staff, and senior/ executive management, or those in different disciplines – in relation to specific principles or tasks;
- e) examples of efforts made to undertake the tasks and/ or address the barriers and their outcome;
- f) particular principles or tasks for which compliance remains difficult;
- g) sustainability of ORD implementation arrangements;
- h) opportunities or benefits which have arisen from this work;
- i) principles or tasks which are being met particularly well, or examples which could be helpful to others.

The topic guide was adapted over the course of the interviews to focus on arising issues in more depth.

3.3.4. Data analysis

Audio records were anonymised and transcribed by an external transcription service. Transcripts were coded using NVivo Version 20 software, and codes were analysed and developed, using a Thematic Analysis approach (47). An initial coding framework was prepared, related to key questions/issues. Following an initial round of inductive coding the coding framework was adapted and transcripts were coded in full using the adapted framework. In the development of themes, codes were considered and compared within and across transcripts, and with reference to field notes made during site visits and additional documentary evidence (3.2). Documents were reviewed (3.2), related to the principles of the Concordat on ORD and associated tasks (3.1) and synthesised narratively (48) in relation to the experiences and concerns of HEI participants. Features and patterns were identified across the dataset. Narrative frameworks were established and assimilated, and recurrent themes developed and interpreted. Shared and dissonant experiences stretched and shaped the narrative framework and thematic analysis. Commonalities and differences were related to participants' positionality, in relation to variety among HEIs, with attention to geography (region/country), scale (e.g. research intensity and research funding), research fields and disciplines. Themes and narratives were interpreted in relation to the overarching aims of the study, with consideration of participant positionality and researcher reflexivity within the analytic process.

3.4. Workshops

Themes, narratives and interpretations were shared with participants in a series of online workshops, through which findings and recommendations were member-checked and co-developed, to provide co-produced recommendations to support UK HEI sector progress in ORD. Online workshops were recorded, with prior informed participant consent, to allow anonymised summaries of participant responses to be incorporated into the findings and recommendations. Workshop participants included UK HEI interviewees and focus group participants, as well as a final workshop oriented around dissemination planning, that included ORD leads from relevant organisations within the wider UK HEI serving ORD ecosystem (e.g. UKRI, other funders, data service providers).

4. Participation

4.1. STAR Participants

A total of 21 HEIs took part in interviews (N=37 interviews), focus groups (N=4) and/or site visits (N=5). As set out in Table 1, HEIs were a diverse geographical mix (by region of England or UK devolved nation).

Table 1. HEI participants by country/region

HEI selection characteristics	Number of HEIs
Country/Region	
England - East Midlands	3
East of England	1
England – London	3
England - North West	2
England - South East	2
England - South West	3
England - Yorkshire and the Humber	2
Scotland	2
Northern Ireland	1
Wales	2
Total HEIs	21

Participating HEIs, as shown in Table 2, were also diverse by scale (approximated by QR funding allocation), and in their disciplinary focus or spread (approximated by units of assessment submitted to the 2021 REF).

Table 2. HEI participants by scale (disciplinary range and funding size)

HEI selection characteristics	Number of HEIs
Number of Units of Assessment	
1 to 5 Units of Assessment	4
6 to 10 Units of Assessment	3
11 to 15 Units of Assessment	6
16 to 30 Units of Assessment	8
QR funding allocation	
£150,000 to £999,999	3
£1,000,000 to £3,999,999	4
£4,000,000 to £12,999,999	7
£13,000,000 to £84, 999, 999	7
Total HEIs	21

One third of participating HEIs were UKRN members, another third were affiliated with UKRN, and a final third were neither members nor affiliates (Table 3).

Table 3. UKRN membership/affiliation

HEI selection characteristics	Number of HEIs
UKRN membership or affiliation	
Member of UKRN/UKRN affiliation	7
UKRN affiliation, but not membership	7
Not a member or affiliate of UKRN	7
Total HEIs	21

HEI workers included institutional executives/strategic leads, directors, managers and workers (see Table 4).

Characteristics of HEI workers	Number of workers
Institutional executive /strategic lead e.g. PVC for Research/Head of Research	2
Professional services director e.g. Head of Research Support/Research Services; Director of Library; Head of Governance, Compliance, Ethics	11
Professional services manager e.g. Open Research Manager; Assistant Head Librarian; Research Excellence Lead; Senior Data Librarian; Information Compliance Manager; Academic Support Manager for Research; Data library manager; Assistant Director Academic and Research Services; Research Integrity manager	13
Professional services worker e.g. Research information officer; Research data officer; Research support librarian; Research information analyst; Research data software engineer; Open research data steward; Research governance officer; Open research coordinator; Open research librarian; Research data librarian; Repository officer; Repository librarian	28
Total HEI workers (including all roles)	54

HEI workers were predominantly situated within library teams, a smaller number (including those with executive roles and ORD oversight) were based in research offices (including combined research, governance and ethics offices); a small number of ORD support workers/managers were based in IT or compliance divisions.

Table 5. Location/Division of Open Research Data roles

Characteristics of HEI workers	Number of workers
Location/division within HEI	
Library services	38

Research (e.g. Research Support; Research Offices; Research and Enterprise; Research and Governance; Research, Governance and Ethics)	12
Other (e.g. IT services; Information Compliance)	4
Total HEI workers	54

4.2 Co-development workshops

Following completion of interviews, focus groups and site visits, preliminary analysis and findings were shared and co-developed with participants, over the course of three online workshops. All HEI participants who had taken part in interviews, focus groups or site visits were invited to the online co-development workshops. Representatives of UKRN-member institutions involved in STAR project funding were also invited.

- the first online ‘preliminary findings’ workshop included 17 participants;
- the second ‘sense checking’ workshop involved 33 participants;
- the final workshop focused on co-developing a dissemination strategy involved 30 participants.

The final workshop included additional participants (not those previously interviewed), who were invited into the final dissemination-focused workshop, because of their links to relevant organisations situated within the wider ORD ecosystem. Additional participants included ORD leads/representatives from the UKRI; Society of College, National and University Libraries (SCONUL); Wellcome; OpenAIRE; Digital Curation Centre; British Academy; and Research Libraries UK (RLUK).

In addition, project discussion meetings (not recorded/formally analysed, but used to sense check co-developed findings) were held with those working on ORD in a number of other UK organisations (e.g. UKRI, Wellcome, Digital Curation Centre, British Academy).

5. Concordat implementation tasks

As outlined (3.1. above), in the early stages of the UKRN STAR project, staff at the DCC worked with sector experts and the STAR project to derive a 16 item implementation task list from the ten Concordat principles (45). Table 6 sets out the Concordat on ORD implementation task list (colour shading relates to progress; see key and 4.3., below).

Table 6. Concordat on ORD implementation task list

Principle (summary)	Tasks for institutions implied by the full text of that principle
1. Open access to research data is an enabler of high-quality research, a facilitator of innovation and safeguards good research practice.	a. Institutions should have policies, practices and culture that recognise the value of open data and the work done to enable it throughout the research process.
	b. Institutions should provide appropriate access to infrastructure systems and services to enable their researchers to make research data open and usable.
2. There are sound reasons why the openness of research data may need to be restricted but any restrictions must be justified and justifiable.	c. Institutions should have verifiable and transparent processes of oversight to guide decisions on whether, when and how data may be made available in some form, to reflect situations where (e.g.) data relates to or is derived from individuals, or has commercial sensitivity, or third-party intellectual property rights.
	d. Institutional policies and guidance should acknowledge that on a case-by-case basis sharing be proportionate to the level of risk associated with the data.
3. Open access to research data carries a significant cost, which should be respected by all parties.	e. Institutions should acknowledge that infrastructure, training, staff support, and progress reviews for open and FAIR research have significant costs and they should have procedures in place to ensure funding of costs within the dual support system.
4. The right of the creators of research data to reasonable first use is recognised.	f. Institutional research data policies must allow the possibility of an initial embargo period before data availability and reuse.
	g. Data management plans should address embargo requests.
5. Use of others' data should always conform to legal, ethical, and regulatory frameworks including appropriate acknowledgement.	h. Institutions should provide support (such as training, guidance, advice and policies) on legal, ethical, and professional frameworks of research integrity as related to issues of open data. This support should cover both appropriate citation and acknowledgement of others' work, and provision of a preferred citation for underlying data and other relevant outputs including research software.
	i. Institutional policies should recognise contributions to shared/open datasets in academic appointment, promotion, research assessment and research funding decisions.

	j. Formal recognition should make use of responsible metrics for tracking research data use and impact, such as data citations.
6. Good data management is fundamental to all stages of the research process and should be established at the outset.	k. Institutions should provide access to the necessary infrastructure to enable researchers to manage their data effectively throughout the research process.
	l. Institutions should provide guidance to researchers throughout the research process on the correct and relevant data management and storage methodologies for that research field.
	m. Institutions should support and make use of shared research infrastructure.
	n. Institutions should provide researchers with training and support in research data management.
7. Data curation is vital to make data useful for others and for long-term preservation of data	o. Where institutions provide access to data repositories, these repositories should be able to guarantee the persistence of the datasets for a reasonable time period.
	p. Institutions should support provision of sufficient metadata for data evaluation and reuse.
	q. Institutions should encourage the use of non-proprietary formats.
8. Data supporting publications should be accessible by the publication date and should be in a citeable form.	r. Where institutions provide access to data (and, where possible, software) repositories, these repositories should enable datasets and related software to be citable, for example by providing them with a persistent identifier.
	s. Institutional policies should require that data underpinning publications should as default be retained for at least ten years in a citeable form.
	t. Institutions should provide guidance on relevant preservation policies and/or retention schedules.
9. Support for the development of appropriate data skills is recognised as a responsibility for all stakeholders.	u. Institutions should provide researcher training opportunities in an organised and professional manner.
	v. Institutions should support data science through skills development and career pathways.
10. Regular reviews of progress towards open research data should be undertaken.	w. Institutions should undertake regular reviews to monitor their progress in implementing their responsibilities under the Concordat on ORD, register issues to be addressed, and identify and share best practice.
	x. Institutions should demonstrate a long-term commitment to open data.

Key	
	Limited progress on Principle/Tasks (little indication of progress)
	Partial progress on Principle/Tasks (progress in some but not all aspects)
	Considerable progress on Principle/Tasks (strong signs of progress)

6. Results

Synthesis of findings from documentary review, interviews, focus groups, site visits and co-development workshops

This section outlines the main findings and inferences from them, in three sections: progress; barriers (the situation); and barriers (causes and potential solutions).

6.1 Institutional ORD progress

Across the diversity of sampled HEIs, progress was strong and widespread in a number of areas (see above, Table 6., Concordat on ORD implementation task list; with considerable progress for principles and tasks shaded in green, and more partial progress for those shaded in blue). Key areas of progress are outlined below.

6.1.1 Progress area 1: ORD Policy increasingly in place

a) Policy that recognised the role of ORD

Institutions of all scales and disciplines had in place ORD policy that recognised the role of ORD.

“Yes ‘Institutions should have policies, practices, and culture that recognise the value of open data.’ So, [our institution is] completely all over this.” [Professional services worker, UK HEI broad disciplinary range, highest bracket QR funding]

Principle 1 of the Concordat on ORD; promoting the value of open research data (see Table 6, ‘Task a.’) was mostly well met. There was some inconsistency in the status of ‘ORD policy’; some ORD policy was ‘drafted’, but awaiting formal executive review/ratification; some was contained in subsections or statements within broader data (rather than standalone ORD) policies. However, high level policy statements promoting the value of ORD and commitments to making institutionally-generated research data open, were prevalent across institutions and regardless of differing levels of QR funding and disciplinary range or focus.

b) Policy on ORD implementation

Policy that described and committed to specific ORD implementation processes was evident in some institutions, but not so clearly specified in others.

“I mean there’s... the open research statement ... that really talks about, you know, the benefits of open research... it might talk about fair data, but it probably won’t go into a great level of detail.” [Professional services Director, UK HEI broad disciplinary range, highest bracket QR funding]

Commonly, ORD implementation policy, plans, or guidance, committed institutions and their associated research communities to:

- the development of infrastructures, repositories, training and support to enable ORD implementation (Table 6, Principle 1., task b., Principle 6. task I. and n.);
- statements relating to embargos/first use of data, justifiable and transparent restricted access, ethical considerations, commercial and intellectual property rights

(Table 6. Principles 2, 4, 5, with some, though not all, related implementation tasks addressed).

- standards for data curation and longevity of storage and access (aspects of Principle 7), data availability for journal publications (Principle 8), and in some cases, the requirement for all HEI research data to be deposited and, where possible, openly published.

Institutional ORD commitments and requirements tended to be set out more clearly in ORD guidance and training material, than in higher level policy statements. It was not unusual for data publication and retention requirements to be laid out in data management policy and guidance, rather than standalone ORD policy.

c) Less tightly specified implementation commitments

Some institutions made high level policy statements without clarifying the detail of implementation plans; implied research requirements were not reinforced by monitoring or compliance systems or processes.

“I think the policy says that the university’s asking everyone to make their data open. They don’t [laughs].” [L_013_S]

There were distinct areas of weaker policy coverage, implementation commitment and guidance:

- The issue of ORD cost responsibility (e.g. data curation, repository storage, data oversight, ORD training and skills development), and the funding of ORD costs, including shared funding (Principle 3), were not reliably addressed.
- Monitoring and compliance evaluation processes and the metrics and methods for tracking ORD publication, reuse and impact (Principle 5, task j.) were not clearly set out.
- Similarly, there were major gaps in relation to recognition, rewards and promotion linked to ORD publication performance and impacts (Principle 5, task i.), in many, though not all, institutions. A few institutions were notably ahead here in relation to promotion, having already brought ORD achievements into formal promotion criteria, often as an outcome of sustained attention and effort on the part of ORD workers.

d) Overall: diffusely spread but supportive ORD policy

Institutional ORD policy statements typically extolled the value of ORD. HEI ORD guidance set out required standards of ORD practice and supportive HEI ORD infrastructure. However, the coverage of Concordat principles and of implementation tasks (Table 6.) was patchy. The green shaded sections of Table 6. show areas of most consistent coverage. There was mixed/fragmentary or limited/missing coverage in some key areas (blue-shaded sections and white-shaded sections of Table 6, respectively). Particularly, gaps were evident for principles and tasks related to evaluation, oversight, metrics, costing, awards and promotion.

As noted, for some institutions, standalone ORD policy was well-established, for others, open research data was covered, but less distinctly, as a subsection of data management policy, research governance and strategic plans. This did not always impact on the substance of the ORD policy statements (what was said about ORD commitments and requirements was often similar). Some ORD policies were less established, in some cases awaiting review, revision, or redraft, and formal executive ratification. However, regardless of the formal status of ORD

policy, guidance on ORD available to institutional staff and researchers, was evident across sampled HEIs, either held within policy documents (e.g. specific ORD or broader data management policy) or in policy-adjacent places, that set out expectations on standards of practice for researchers (e.g. guidance on data management for researchers/staff). HEI ORD policy was usually readily accessible to staff and summarised for on HEI websites, with information regularly updated by ORD specialist workers/teams.

e) The status of the Concordat on ORD within policy

Institutional ORD policy only sometimes referred directly to the Concordat on ORD.

“I mean, in terms of the policy itself, it's a set of policy statements and outlining of responsibilities. It doesn't directly refer to the Concordat, but it does reference UKRI's common principles on data...it's largely aligned with those common principles... there's not a lot in there that is a strong mandate...” [T_032_a]

Some interviewees had been directly involved in drafting their institution's ORD policy and were ORD specialists, who were familiar with the principles of the Concordat on ORD. Some ORD policy explicitly referred to the Concordat on ORD. Others said that the Concordat on ORD had been discussed as part of ORD policy development processes. Others referred instead to UKRI guidance or to the FAIR principles. In summary, the Concordat on ORD was widely recognised, often appeared to have informed policy development, but was not necessarily explicitly referenced and was not the only conduit for HEI ORD policy development. Regardless of the status of the Concordat on ORD, there was considerable policy conformity that tended to align with the core principles of the Concordat and in the detail (and gaps) in coverage.

In summary, UKHEI policy documents demonstrated a high-level commitment to ORD progress, with priorities that strongly cohered to the principles of the Concordat on ORD (whether explicitly or not). However, policy statements could be relatively high level statements of value, not always tied to clearly specified implementation strategies, and coverage of the whole set of principles (and in relation to associated implementation tasks) was more fragmentary.

6.1.2 Progress area 2: ORD implementation/infrastructure provision

In distinct areas there were clear signs of ORD implementation progress.

a) ORD specialists in post, providing dedicated support

Institutions at all scales had created specialist ORD roles and attracted workers with expertise in ORD to these positions. ORD specialists performed multiple dedicated ORD services (Table 6. Principle 1. Task b.; relevant also to Principle 6. Task l., and Task n.; Principle 7. Task p., Principle 8. Task t.; Principle 9. Task u.).

“... the research data management team that I manage, look after [the institution's] data repository, they do all of the intake metadata verification support for that process. They also do data management planning training for the university as a whole, so PhD students, academics, whatever.” [E_035_S]

ORD specialists were involved in:

- drafting (and delivering) ORD policy, guidance and implementation strategies;
- providing ORD support services for academic communities;
- supporting and advising data management planning processes;
- supporting and advising on data curation and metadata formulation (often involving detailed work checking project data and meta data, and supporting upload and publication within HEI repositories, issuing DOIs for published ORD);
- providing ORD training and infrastructure support to researchers and postgraduates;
- procurement and development of institutional repository services;
- providing accessible information, guidance and training in accessible formats to highly diverse research communities (e.g. easy read, user-friendly guidance available on institutional webpages) to researchers/teaching staff and postgraduate students;
- sharing skills and knowledge to support institutional ORD practices and standards (e.g. ethical requirements, consent processes, data access statements, repository use, data curation, meta data).

b) Small ORD teams/partial roles

Larger institutions, with greater funding, more often had small teams in place (a fulltime equivalent, or more than one qualified and experienced ORD worker, working alongside other data specialists, IT specialists, librarians and sometimes ethicists). Some established ORD workers had been involved in trailblazing work on ORD policy, implementation and institutional guidance over a number of years and also offered ORD guidance to HEIs beyond their own institution (20, 49). Smaller institutions more often had one ORD specialist, perhaps more recently in post, and often in a part-time, or partial ORD role.

“We’ve got one person now, and a lot of these policies and these frameworks feel like they just pile responsibilities on that one person. A lot of places they don’t even have the one person. When I first started the job, I did a lot of introductory data management type training... I met a lot of people who do like a little bit of repository manager job and a little bit of bibliometrics.” [J_015_S]

c. Dedicated institutional repository provision

Across the full range of institutions, repositories were in place enabling institutionally-supported storage, curation, publication and reuse of ORD. Researchers were supported by HEI data specialists to make use of these facilities (see *Table 6. Principle 1, Task b.; Principle 6. Tasks k. and l.; Principle 7., Task o.; Principle 8, Task r.*).

“We use Pure as a data repository, so we manage datasets, we also create DOIs for those and we also manage the long term digital preservation... We use a product called Arkivum and that looks after all of our datasets... we require, for anyone who does research at our university... if they are the primary investigator responsible for the data, then that has to go into our repository ...” [V_036_S]

Some HEI repository systems had been recently upgraded, with considerable data specialist work researching and procuring repository services, and moving existing data from old to new storage systems. Some larger institutions had their own bespoke repository software and IT support teams. Smaller institutions more often bought-in external, private-provider managed, data management software systems (e.g. Figshare, Pure), enabling institutions of all scales to offer dedicated, institutionally-supported, ORD repository space to their research communities. Data specialists described researching ORD repository software providers as part of procurement processes, including seeking advice and feedback from data specialists at similarly positioned HEIs already using relevant data management and ORD publishing systems.

c) The status and scale of institutional ORD repositories ('repositories of last resort')

In our sample, ORD specialists typically described their institutional repository as a 'repository of last resort', advising researchers to seek out alternative, more appropriate, discipline-focused (accessible and visible to those working within a given field of research), research-community favoured, repository options, rather than taking-up (more limited and less focused) HEI-managed repository space.

Institutional repository storage limitations were noted as a concern for ORD teams, alongside concerns about researchers' poor awareness of appropriate alternatives, and about the insufficiency of funds accounted for within the research project budgets, for long-term open repository storage of very large datasets.

However, more often, ORD repositories were relatively newly established and institutions/ORD workers were keen for their research communities to make use of these, and to be able to demonstrate and encourage a flourishing institutional culture of open data publication and data sharing. As such, repository limitations were not the most pressing current concern, even if they remained a real issue. In this context, ORD teams primarily sought to encourage researchers to share data, and did not place restrictions on the use of the institutional repository (beyond those that related to data curation standards, or specific commercial, proprietorial or ethical concerns). While recommending that researchers might find and use more appropriate alternatives, they did not inhibit open data publication because of repository capacity concerns. The emphasis (in policy, guidance and in descriptions of in person support) at this time, was placed on encouragement of data sharing and FAIR standards of practice.

However, it was clear that for most institutions, without more funding to expand ORD repository capacity, this position was plausible only in the context of relatively limited ORD activities among research communities. For the most part, institutional ORD repositories were relatively newly established, and given current rates of ORD publication, far from reaching their current ORD storage limits. However, for institutions with more established ORD repositories, and with research communities more experienced in open data publication, the conversations around repository capacity were increasingly focused (with explicit – though still not yet prohibitive - data publication restrictions coming into play for those with more established data repositories).

Institutional repositories, as currently set up, assume the availability of a wider ORD ecosystem, containing a plethora of alternative, reputable, discipline-focused, national/international open data repository options, available evenly across disciplines. A future in which ORD creation among HEI research communities is fully normalised, may still require coordination of additional, highly visible, diverse, expansive, accessible, well-supported and promoted, funded and sustainable, data repository provisions.

As such, in the future it may be that institutional repositories contain less data, and more metadata, providing an openly accessible record of all institutionally-created research data, but for the most part allowing data that is openly published elsewhere to be readily located. This may already be the position for some larger institutions (those wealthiest by QR funding and with the most expansive and mature dedicated institutional data repositories), where data policy statements require all institutionally-associated research data to be either stored, or linked (using appropriate metadata to find and locate the data) to the institutionally-managed data repository, in an openly-published format, wherever possible. This enables the institution both to monitor ORD arising from research it hosts, and to demonstrate that it has enabled data curation.

d) Routine ORD guidance and training for researchers and postgraduates

Data specialists described routinely providing accessible guidance and offering regular training opportunities in ORD to researchers and to postgraduates (Table 6., Principle 1, Task b., Principle 5. Task h., Principle 9. Task u.). This was often a core designated part of ORD data specialist roles.

“...what we do quite well is providing some of the guidance around these things, we have intranet pages, quite ...detailed intranet pages for staff and students around guidance in various aspects of research data management... Similarly ... providing training as part of that and factoring that into research integrity... [with] online training that all researchers have to do... that’s been established for quite a long time and ... embedded in various things like staff development...” [G_010_S]

Some postgraduate courses had mandated ORD training elements, with uptake of ORD training typically much stronger among postgraduates. Uptake was often reported as much weaker among researchers and teaching staff. This may relate in part to the heft of established research cultures, and limited links within many research fields between ORD outputs and research impact and recognition, and in formalised links between accomplishments in ORD activities and formal professional development, career pathways and promotion criteria (Principle 5. Task i., and Principle 9, Task v.). Similarly, lack of monitoring and compliance checking both by HEIs and funders, was felt to reduce the push to undertake non-compulsory ORD training among research communities where ORD publication was not yet a familiar research practice.

ORD specialists observed disparities between considerable ORD training uptake among postgraduates, in contrast with more senior research community members, and postgraduate

supervisors, who engaged much less in ORD training. This disparity seemed prone to increase reliance on ORD specialists as proxy advisors in relation to postgraduate ORD publication tasks.

e) Accessible ORD guidance

ORD specialists routinely provided guidance, in accessible, easy-read formats, openly available to researchers, on relevant institutional webpages. More established teams sometimes had much more tightly developed resources, and clearer statements to support researchers' decision making processes (for instance, in relation to open, restricted or closed data, confidentiality, consent, and data availability in the case of human data research, and data access statements), and clearly spelt out processes for data preparation, including links to precise data curation guidance. However, there was strong alignment in the guidance offered to researchers to encourage and support research communities to publish ORD and to make their data 'as open as possible, as closed as necessary' (*Principle 2. Task c. and d.; Principle 4. Task f. and g.; Principle 5. Task h.; Principle 6, Task l.; Principle 7. Task p.; Principle 8. Tasks r., s., and t.*). Notably:

- FAIR standards were commonly embedded within institutional ORD training and guidance;
- Guidance offered clarity on decision-making processes in relation to deidentified human data, relevant consent processes, and associated ethical concerns;
- Support and guidance were available to assist with ORD planning as part of data management plans to support funding applications;
- Intellectual property concerns, embargo provisions, data availability statements and ORD to support publications were especially well-supported through personal input from data specialists and the availability of accessible guidance.

The exceptions to progress in this area, related to:

- guidance on ORD in the case of commercial interests, was typically less well-integrated within ORD guidance (in policy statements and in interview accounts). Researchers were usually guided to seek specialist advice from separate teams focused on commerce and enterprise, and to make use of embargos and other devices to support (eventual if not immediate) open research data publication. However, whether or not ORD is a priority issue for innovation and commercialisation teams remains unclear. Professional support teams providing guidance to researchers on commercial contracts were often situated separately from, and lacked regular contact with, ORD specialists (and were not interviewed as part of the STAR project);
- financing ORD work; ORD specialists reported a lack of clear guidance to support researchers in costing and budgeting ORD work in research applications, with examples of researchers considerably under-costing the time required for data curation, and the costs of repository storage;
- the metrics of evaluation and any ways in which ORD work and impact would be routinely recognised, captured, monitored and rewarded as part of research evaluation and compliance exercises.

The ORD advice offered to researchers by enterprise, innovation, and contractual professional support teams, finance and compliance teams, may benefit from greater scrutiny and further input, contact and integration with ORD specialists and the overarching ORD guidance that is available to researchers. Without this engagement, there is a risk that commerce-focused teams may be encouraging undue caution and restriction in relation to ORD and commercial interests. Those working on funding applications may be encouraged to unhelpfully downplay or exclude ORD costs in fear of reducing the competitiveness of applications (if costs are not established and others are not appropriately pricing-in this work). Greater clarity around assessment and metrics would allow researchers to more effectively record their ORD activities, and would support monitoring, evaluation and compliance assessment, relevant also to formal institutional rewarding of ORD activities.

6.1.3 Progress area 3: ORD practices evident within institutional research communities

a) Examples of local research community ORD practices.

All interviewees were able to offer recent examples of successful ORD practices within their institution (researchers making their data openly available for reuse).

“... it was international open access week ... at the same time as us launching Figshare, so one of the events we had was a poster competition for staff and students. So any data that utilised open access data or was making conscious steps in being as open as possible... there were quite a few in social sciences, there was one about facial recognition, we had law, there were a couple of science ones as well and computer science...” [N_031_S]

ORD specialists reported supporting researchers to make their data openly available in citable formats, including via their university’s repository facilities. Often the spur to openly publish research data, in a citeable format, stemmed from journal publication requirements (rather than institutional open data policy statements).

“When it comes to open data we’ve had some success. It’s fair to say that the success has mostly been based on when there’s been requirements for that with journal publications and that’s probably one of the crucial bits for this...” [K_020_S]

ORD specialist support in these cases often appeared to be detailed and time-consuming, including considerable advisory work, data and metadata scrutiny and guidance. ORD specialists took their responsibility to inform and encourage seriously, and described spending generous amounts of time exploring ORD possibilities and explaining ORD processes with disciplinarily diverse researchers within their institution. The intensive data curation and repository support ORD workers described, aligned with their commitment to the cause of ORD, and to strengthening both the quality and quantity of institutional outputs, in the context of a widespread recognition of researchers’ limited data curation skills. However, it was clear that the levels of support currently provided by ORD specialist workers, to relatively small numbers of researchers, would be unsustainable at any much greater scale. At greater scale, the quality of institutional ORD outputs cannot be entirely dependent on the fine-grained attention of ORD workers; there is a need for researchers and/or their teams to gain necessary skills and to take on greater responsibility in this area.

Some institutions had annual ORD awards or showcase events, to celebrate ORD data accomplishments. However, some ORD workers spoke of their reluctance to single out researchers in their institutions who were already diligently publishing ORD. These ORD workers noted their discomfort with the idea of creating ‘ORD Champion’ roles. There was genuine concern that this kind of honorary status would not be welcomed by already overburdened researchers, if, being recognised as a source of ORD expertise and guidance, meant additional, unsustainable, workload.

Workload pressures and fear of overwhelm, for both ORD workers and researchers (who were often also lecturers and/or practitioners, and carried additional departmental and/or institutional administrative workloads) were palpable concerns. The additional and time-consuming nature of ORD data curation work appeared to be poorly recognised or accounted for in the context of a lumbering research culture, already dependent on heavy staff workloads that tended towards overload and overwhelm. This tension was noted across the board, but was most apparent among smaller HEIs with less QR funding to draw on, where staff appeared to take on compromising workloads in acute awareness of an ever-present existential threat to the survival of their institution.

b) Identifiable research communities actively engaged with institutional ORD processes

HEIs recognised research communities with strong ORD interests, skills and practices (particularly HEIs with research and teaching in STEM-oriented disciplines, see 1.4, Disciplinary differences and readiness):

“...we have a school of psychological and behavioural sciences, they are very passionate about reproducibility and they’re quite engaged in those issues.” [J_042_S]

Some of these researchers had been involved in early EPSRC funding initiatives and were closely connected to ORD infrastructure developments within their institution. Others were part of research communities with long experience in international ORD database collaborations, who were less likely to seek institutional ORD support or repository space, or to be involved in nascent HEI ORD oversight committees (meaning their substantial experience and expertise in ORD, though institutionally recognised, remained peripheral to institutional developments in ORD). However, those with backgrounds in experimental psychology, in particular, were notably more engaged in HEI ORD developments, both as UKRN Leads and representatives on ORD-relevant oversight committees (reflecting recent attention to ORD concerns, following high profile reproducibility concerns in Psychology).

More reticent research communities remained largely disengaged, though there were examples of in-depth engagement work, especially in smaller institutions, to build understanding of the purpose and value of ORD among diverse research communities.

“...for instance, we had a long discussion, didn’t we, yesterday, with a member of staff who is a sculptor, talking about what data could be for them.” [P_026_S_A]

c) Normalisation of postgraduate ORD training and publication

Postgraduates are increasingly required to undertake training in data management that includes training in ORD. As part of final dissertation outputs, there were examples of

postgraduate research data being openly published in HEI repositories and/or the retention of links to openly accessible postgraduate data held on other platforms (e.g. videos of arts performances).

“I think one thing that we are working on in terms of education and raising that awareness is I think getting in at PGR level, and we have managed to kind of tweak our PGR code of practice to introduce data access statements.” U_034_S_E]

6.1.4 Progress, in summary

Interviews, policy, and guidance documents, suggested steady progress within UK HEIs in terms of both the policy and infrastructure needed to make exemplary ORD possible; researchers were actively encouraged, offered routine training, provided with intensive personal support and guidance, and where needed, institutional ORD repository space was readily available. As a result, research data, stemming from UK HEI research, is increasingly openly accessible for reuse, across broad-ranging research disciplines.

6.2 Barriers to ORD progress: the situation

6.2.1 Background: Stalled progress

Despite significant progress, and regardless of institutional income, scale, or disciplinary range, it was clear that the scale of ORD activities, relative to the scale of overall institutional research activities, remains limited and exceptional, rather than culturally normalised and ubiquitous.

Institutions appeared to have successfully and diligently carved out paths that make high quality (e.g. FAIR) ORD possible. These ORD paths appeared to be well-constructed (including highly skilled workers and well supported, technically advanced, ORD repository databases) and fit for current levels of ORD activity. However, these infrastructures were not yet operating at sufficient scale, or growing at sufficient pace, to support institution-wide levels of ORD activity, especially given limited expertise in data preparation, curation and repository use among research communities. There was a sense that, across UKHEIs, despite strong statements of ORD purpose and commitment, the prioritisation and further ramping up of infrastructure development needed for ORD to become a normalised part of everyday research culture remains, at least for now, on hold.

Institutionally speaking, ORD practices could be described as fully and functionally **possible, encouraged and supported**, with exemplary ORD practices demonstrably enabled across sampled UK HEIs. However, ORD activity remained for the most part an **exceptional, not routine** activity. Making research data open was not common research practice across all disciplines, and those making research data openly available remained in the minority for most research communities. While policy statements described a commitment to making all research data open (though closed where necessary), current levels of ORD implementation, though executed to a high standard, seemed to better fit a more limited goal of making exemplary ORD publication possible.

The further goal of ORD normalisation, that would require a considerable scaling up of ORD activities, and that would carry considerable resource implications, remained a future concern,

rather than a current priority. This meant that while there was steady and diligent progress, that was aligned with the principles and implementation tasks of Concordat on ORD, more intensive scaling-up activities appeared stalled

6.2.2 Anticipation of change

Data specialists (both those with more executive /strategic roles and those in support roles) conveyed a sense of anticipation. They described waiting to hear if and when external levers (e.g. stringent REF criteria) might be brought into play that would cement the institutional status and prioritisation of ORD and force a shift in the pace of uptake.

“...until we know what the rules are [the next REF specifications] there’s a little bit of hesitancy to go too far just because you don’t know what you’re going to be measured on...” [J_042_S]

6.2.3 Undercurrent tensions

Waiting for an external steer before attempting to scale up ORD capabilities reflected undercurrent tensions, that situated ORD implementation within the context of wider institutional financial, resource and workload pressures and sustainability concerns (and at worst, existential threats). ORD specialists were often working at capacity in their own (often partial/sole worker) ORD roles. They were genuinely concerned about the impact (on the institution, professional support staff, and research communities) of any poorly-considered, inappropriate, sweeping change in ORD requirements.

“...in the same way that I’m stretched, our academics are stretched. We have very few academics on research-only contracts. So you’re not just doing research. You’re teaching. You’re doing research-led teaching. You’re maybe trying to get some grant funding. Maybe you’re trying to bring in some collaborative partners. You’ve got to be a personal tutor for the Level 6. You’ve got to be a programme leader for that. You’ve got to be involved in open days, in recruitment. So everyone’s spread thin...” [L_013_S]

At a time of financial constraint, institutions were proud of their ORD capabilities, but cautious to move further or faster, without a clear indication of sector-wide movement, funder ORD requirements, and financial returns (or at least future security) on any further ORD investment. Internal drivers (whether through bottom-up research community interests or top-down strategic interests) to scale up efforts beyond current ORD capabilities, appeared tightly constrained. In this context, ORD specialists and institutional leads looked tentatively to external leverage (e.g. UKRI or REF criteria) to drive up the pace and scale of ORD progress within their institution.

“I would like to say it is becoming a norm. But it is not doing it as fast as something like Open Access publishing. [Interviewer: Ah, and why is that?] Because there’s no one waving a big stick... Love it or hate it, the REF has changed Open Access forever because there is no need for an incentive. You’ve got a big stick with REF written on it. But open data... [is] being done on a level ‘because you want to’, ‘because it’s the right thing to do’. You’re still in ‘carrot territory’ with the data...” [E_035_S]

Potential drivers of further change were often presented as carrots or sticks. The 'sticks' were changes to REF criteria, or to other major funder requirements. 'Carrots' were incentives, linked to intrinsic values, impacts, recognition and rewards. The levers of REF and funding conditions were viewed as useful and at times necessary, mechanisms for change. However, they were recognised as heavy-handed, 'top-down' approaches, that risked unintended consequences and unsustainable workloads. ORD workers were committed to open data and to institutional ORD policy, but described the tension in their twin role, simultaneously serving institutional policy, funders' requirements and (sometimes) formal regulatory standards, and providing professional support to overburdened research community members to deliver on ORD standards, in the context of multiple other demands. 'Sticks' were associated with the possibility of action and institution-wide shifts in ORD activities, but also with considerable jeopardy, especially in financially constrained circumstances, where institutions and research communities were already recognised as subject to significant resource, capacity and workload pressures.

Values-driven change was, in principle, favoured, where shared values underpin an appreciation of proposed changes, allowing change to be driven from the ground up and to be built on intrinsic and tangible benefits and rewards. Values-driven change best preserves the bond between institutions, professional service staff and research communities, and allows ORD workers to more easily straddle their dual role, driving institutional standards of practice, while supporting (in this idealised case, communities of willing and motivated) researchers to meet these standards.

However, the more realistic picture painted by ORD workers was one of relative weakness in the bottom-up, values-driven impetus towards change. Uptake of the training regularly delivered by ORD workers was patchy unless it was mandated (for instance for postgraduates and occasionally supervisors, in some institutions). ORD workers offered numerous examples of researchers' prevailing inexperience with the technical requirements of ORD publication and reuse, and the extent to which ORD continued to be an irrelevance for many. The value of ORD appeared remote and uncertain among many research communities. Bottom-up, values-driven change is unlikely while this continues to be the case. ORD workers continued to emphasise the value and purpose of ORD activities in their teaching and in contacts with researchers, and in this hopeful spirit, provided detailed support and encouragement to develop researchers ORD skills, confidence and practices. However, they also acknowledged limited uptake of ORD training and that researchers seeking support for ORD activities remained a minority in most research communities, and that the level of ORD skills within most research communities remained weak.

Despite considerable work, progress and commitments, and the employment of skilled and motivated, dedicated ORD workers, institutions often appeared to have reached a temporary plateau in ORD roll out, and awaited (a much anticipated) sector-wide external steer (e.g. new UKRI or REF requirements) to galvanise further implementation.

Areas of stalled progress included a number of important, consistently raised, concerns that require attention. Attending to these concerns is important to the next phase of sector-wide implementation work.

6.2.4 Concerns and barriers to successful ORD implementation

In the remaining report we attend to ORD implementation concerns that were consistently identified by STAR participants. Each concern was presented as substantially unresolved and, without further work, as a barrier to progress in ORD rollout. Each was felt to need a mix of attention, collaboration, institutional but also sometimes sector-wide agreement, and action, ideally before any further development in institutional ORD requirements or scaling up of ORD

activities. These are issues that require leadership, purposeful intervention, engagement, planning and action and may benefit from external support and coordination.

The risks in not attending to identified concerns, before scaling up ORD, are that:

1) institutions and researchers may be unable to meet the costs and demands of required ORD activities, ORD workers may be unsustainably overloaded, leading to disregard and failure of ORD requirements, impacting more severely, and with more negative impacts and threats to future funding, on already hard-pressed institutions;

2) external (e.g. UKRI funding conditions, or REF criteria) ORD directives will be poorly formulated in ways that could reduce, instead of bolster, the integrity and excellence of diverse research communities, their outputs and contributions;

3) where the burden of demands is felt to be unreasonable and/or unjustified, overloaded researchers and professional support staff may become overly strained and demoralised and exit from research activities.

4) increasing and normalising ORD outputs will not result in the achievement of intended benefits (e.g. increased transparency, efficiency, advances in knowledge, public trust); the costs of ORD activities may outweigh perceived benefits;

Current constraints in relation to faster HEI ORD progress or greater expectations can be seen as a legitimate institutional response both to commonly felt institutional tensions (e.g. financial and workload pressures) and significant unresolved ORD implementation issues (barriers to progress, see below). Sampled institutions were typically aware of these challenges, and in some cases were actively working on remedies, but there were no cases in which institutions had fully and effectively resolved these issues, nor where they had plans in place to comprehensively address these concerns.

Unlike areas where there were clear signs of implementation progress (e.g. see section 6.1, above), action in the concern areas was either limited, or had not resulted in resolution of the identified challenges. There were also no strong indications of coordinated external support to address these issues (e.g. UKRI, other funders, ORD data repository and database providers, though all were recognised to be engaging in some more piecemeal activities relevant to the identified areas of concern). As such, there appears to be a need for renewed effort at multiple levels (the institutional level, research community/disciplinary level, and wider ecosystem level) to more concertedly attend to these concerns.

The description of identified concerns and barriers to successful ORD implementation, is followed by a series of co-developed recommendations. The identification of concerns, barriers and recommendations is intended to support proactive, ecosystem-wide, focus and action on these issues, prior to and in preparation for the widely anticipated roll out of further ORD requirements (in particular more stringent REF criteria related to ORD activities either in 2029 or subsequently).

6.3 Barriers to ORD progress: the causes and potential ways forward

6.3.1 Introductory remarks

The question of uncertain value and purpose runs through a whole range of the concerns and challenges, that were repeatedly identified by STAR interviewees and focus group participants.

Some of these challenges are associated with the need to attend to ‘what has this got to do with me/my work?’ questions. The terminology of ‘open research data’ can be off-putting and alienating for researchers from diverse disciplines, especially those that are not oriented around ‘data’, and across institutional communities that include practitioners and teachers whose HEI work is not oriented around research or data. Even among research communities attuned to the concepts of research and data, the value of engaging in ORD activities is not always clear or obvious, especially among researchers working in areas where it is hard to imagine engagement with ORD outputs (e.g. where there may be little or no obviously beneficial scope or audience for reuse, and where data sharing and reuse practices are not an established part of knowledge building work within their discipline).

Other values-based challenges relate to a need, in circumstances of financial and resource constraint, and (as a result) increasingly intense workload pressures, to justify the purpose and value of ORD activities, in relation to the work and costs involved, and competing research priorities. Challenges in this area indicate a need to define processes of institutional or within-discipline review, that would allow researchers, funders and institutions, to estimate the work, time, and costs of proposed ORD outputs and to consider these fairly, in relation to a realistic assessment of potential impacts. This could mean attending to the ‘what has this got to do with me/my work?’ questions, by at times allowing for the possibility of exemption from ORD activities, so that researchers can avoid wasteful and unwarranted ORD activities, where on consideration these are not sufficiently justified.

Values-based concerns also lead to recognition of the need for greater inclusion in the ORD implementation agenda, and especially to actively engage diverse and currently disengaged researcher communities in institutional processes of ORD implementation and oversight. Without this engagement, those contributing to the framing of ORD requirements, review, evaluation and exemption procedures are unlikely to include the research communities who are most likely, without their inclusion, to be most negatively impacted by future ORD requirements. In particular, the concern is that funding conditions and REF requirements, will impact negatively on the future work, status and funding available to those research communities who are, perhaps entirely justifiably, disengaged from ORD activities.

Other challenges relate to stark gaps in the connection between ORD outputs and palpable impacts, due to a lack of ORD reuse, especially where ORD outputs are unfamiliar both to research communities and potential audiences. Researchers are not yet familiar with identifying target ORD audiences and helping to connect or promote their ORD outputs to these audiences. Those who may benefit from access to ORD may be unfamiliar with relevant databases, and may need support to access and reuse ORD outputs. Mechanisms aimed at strengthening connection between researchers’ ORD outputs and wider community reuse and impact, need to be identified, supported and promoted. Connection between ORD activities and the realisation of the overarching vision and values that underpins ORD implementation plans, needs to be made palpable through greater recognition of tangibly connected ORD outputs and explicit impacts.

Other values-based challenges relate to the emergent status of ORD, and the associated invisibility of current, poorly recognised and accommodated, ORD workloads. Attending to the

need for values-based processes of research project review that include careful consideration of proposed ORD activities, in relation to the work, costs, and impacts, would lay the ground also for making explicit the time, work and costs involved in currently invisible ORD labour. Without these kinds of deliberate review processes in place, ORD work is not currently sufficiently costed, justified, or accounted for in project work plans, undermining the time and attention researchers are able to give to ORD tasks and skills development, especially alongside multiple challenging project priorities, and other roles and responsibilities.

Remaining values-based concerns move beyond questions of the intrinsic and tangible values, purposes, impacts and justifications for ORD activities, to the question of externally mediated incentives, rewards and recognition. These relate to the ways that institutions and other players in the wider ORD ecosystem can demonstrate their valuing of ORD activities and help to raise the profile of ORD activities, stimulate greater reuse, encourage researchers to connect ORD activities and outputs to tangible impacts, and commit precious time and project resources to ORD activities, to training and skills development, and to ensuring the standards of practice (e.g. in data preparation and meta-labelling) needed for ORD outputs to hold and realise their value.

6.3.2 The need to attend to uncertain value

As outlined (see 6.1, above), in some fields ORD practices are already normalised. Researchers in these fields directly experience the value of ORD, through their own and others' reuse of open data. The impact of data accessibility and reuse on collaboration, research integrity, resource efficiency and on the advance of knowledge within these fields can be seen as self-evident. In circumstances where knowledge advances are dependent on hugely expensive technologies, or the analysis of vast, time-consuming, data outputs, data sharing promises massive and tangible resource-use efficiencies and accelerated knowledge gain. In these kinds of areas (such as genetics and astrophysics), a shared values-based recognition of the potential for whole-community gain, has driven pioneering collaborative efforts towards ORD infrastructure development and data sharing agreements.

In contrast to this, for researchers in many other research disciplines sharing ORD remains unusual, and the benefits of doing so, remain far from obvious. The intrinsic value of ORD is not yet clear in many disciplines.

“...I think in some cases, they just aren't really aware of it... they're not in a discipline that is data hungry where data policies are heavily pushed by funders, where you've got, you know... kind of processes and policies around that. So, there are subject areas... [ORD] isn't on their radar, there's not really that much incentive. They don't quite recognise, 'What's someone else going to do with my notebooks?' That kind of thing...”
[U_034_S_D]

Making data open has real time, workload and cost implications (training and skills development costs, data curation costs, repository data preservation costs) that must be justified by researchers, by institutions, and by research funders in relation to other research priorities, endeavours and outputs. In times of strongly-felt financial constraint, it makes little sense to commit to laborious and costly ORD activities without genuine prospects for reuse or other benefit to the research field and/or the openly accessible knowledge-base more broadly. In areas of research where the value of ORD remains unclear, endogenously-driven incentives to engage in the additional work of ORD remain weak and are a significant barrier to ORD take-up.

6.3.3 Recognition of STEM-centric terminology, time-consuming translation work and the need to attend to issues of inclusivity

It is by now widely acknowledged that the language and concept of “data” in and of itself can be alienating, especially for researchers working in fields that rarely use tabular, quantitative data, or that are not STEM-based (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics). ORD workers regularly described using alternative words and undertaking (what we have called) “translation work”, to engage disciplinarily diverse research communities, and to make ORD practices inclusive. This could mean defining “data” in more inclusive terms (e.g. “data is any material used to support your assertions”) or providing relevant examples (e.g. “musical recordings are data”).

“you really need to do a kind of a softly, softly advocacy approach... say, for example... you speak to researchers and you get to know their research and you get to identify what potentially could be shared and couldn't be shared and you develop a rapport with them and trust with them...like, for example, when I have one to ones with some of those creative media people and they'll say, oh, I never thought about this... You have to have just a tailored, bespoke conversation or a coffee with a researcher in arts and humanities, so it's a huge investment in time and resourcing...” [X_039_S_b]

Translation work of this kind requires sensitive communication, relationship building and understanding, which can be positive, intellectually stimulating and enjoyable work (e.g. interpreting the meaning and value of “open data” with a sculptor). However, translation work can also be time-consuming for busy ORD workers and can be delicate, exposing tensions. The word ‘data’ is readily alienating, in that it speaks to some, more than other, disciplines and research communities. The question “what does ORD have to do with me and my work?” may be a statement of rebuke rather than curiosity, especially for overloaded researchers with other pressing priorities.

Ensuring greater inclusivity and relevance through the language and examples used in ORD policy and guidance, could lessen the sense that ORD is a STEM-centric issue and may help to encourage and support diverse researchers to more broadly consider the parts of their research and outputs that may be amenable to digitised preservation and could hold value for reuse.

6.3.4 The need to recognise disciplinary and epistemic diversity and variation in the value of ORD

“In terms of is there an appetite? There is certainly, you know, we have adopted this institutional policy. It applies to all our researchers. So, in that sense, there's an aspiration. I think, in reality, when we're talking about priorities on the ground, there are some fields and some things where actually the relative value, you know, the nature of their research data is such that realistically, because, you know, there are some disciplines where you're in that kind of humanity space where a lot of this is about thinking, writing, you know. The data in itself is, you know, it's not raw data, it's not qualitative, quantitative. And therefore, yes, those researchers do kind of struggle to see, 'Is my data valuable?' And in reality, it may not kind of ever make it to the top of their 'To Do List' and it's never going to be a battle that we fight. There's got to be a value to it. But this is where the policy talks about, you know, evaluate the, it's about the value of the data. Where there is data that is of value, we need to make sure that everyone understands what data is of value and requires retention. And therefore, makes those decisions.” [U_034_S_D]

Efforts to galvanise widespread cultural and institutional change have led ORD activities to be encouraged as an almost unqualified good, to be undertaken institution-wide, across all research communities. In the early push to implement ORD policies within institutions, there has been little space to acknowledge the ways in which the value of ORD may vary significantly for different research communities, research projects and research data. In practice, hard-pushed researchers working on short-term contracts, with tight budgets and time frames and competing research impact priorities, do need to consider the value of ORD before committing limited resources to ORD activities.

A familiar type of example is that of a theoretical mathematician's exasperation at being required to identify 'research data' and produce a data management plan. We can imagine the mathematician's research process: perhaps some solitary reading, reflection and insight, idiosyncratic note making and equations, working through mathematical ideas. There is little in this to preserve. Only the notes are tangible and scannable, but unless they were made for sharing, they may be uninterpretable to others, and of little reuse value. A carefully prepared and openly accessible publication that conveys and explains valuable mathematical insights, is more useful to the mathematician's primary research community and to others beyond this. In this case, there may be little, if any, meaningful gain in additional efforts to preserve available ORD. Perhaps a future mathematician, artist, or psychologist intrigued by processes of mathematical working, may find the mathematician's notes interesting, but does this speculative possibility justify the costs of preservation for the mathematician, his institution, or research funders?

Institutional ORD policy, guidance and research ethics committees, highlight the need to recognise legitimate exceptions to ORD, and often set out the kinds of circumstances in which some data can and should, at least temporarily, in some cases, stay 'closed' (e.g. in response to proprietorial or commercial interests, or to avoid identification of personal human data). Justification for these kinds of exceptions is by now well established and widely present in

institutional ORD policy and guidance. The expression ‘as open as possible, as closed as necessary’, as set out in the Concordat on ORD, that refers to these kinds of exceptions, was highly prevalent across institutional policies, guidance and interviews. However, these exceptions are narrow, in that they focus only on the issue of open vs. closed research data. There is an in-built presumption in these exceptions that meaningful research data is/will always be available and should normally always be preserved.

Formalised opportunities or processes to consider more fundamental questions about the value and purpose of proposed ORD activities, that might also justify the legitimate avoidance of ORD activities in some cases, were not apparent in policy documents or guidance. However, it was apparent that without funding conditionality or mandate of ORD practices, a majority of researchers, either through lack of awareness (an omission) or avoidance (a choice), do not yet engage in ORD activities. For this majority, the more fundamental questions of purpose and value, and the way these may relate to costs, workload and other research priorities, remain relevant and possibly significant barriers to wider engagement in ORD practices. Without acknowledging the legitimacy of more fundamental questions of the value and purpose of particular ORD activities and outputs, in relation to particular research endeavours, and without forums to consider these issues as part of research project development, these concerns remain latent, but may also represent an elephant in the room in relation to ORD uptake and values-driven change.

6.3.5 The need to establish processes of review, that attend to the value, quality and purposes of proposed ORD activities, and allow justified exemptions

As things stand, policy and guidance lacks detail on how and when to consider the purpose, quality and value of ORD outputs. Yet the question of ORD purpose and value is highly relevant to institutions, research communities, research projects, research ethics review panels, and funders, all of whom need to be able to justify ORD activities and outputs in relation to ORD costs/harms and impacts.

“I’ve had quite a number of conversations with psychiatrists, psychologists, social scientists, where it’s risk versus reward versus effort versus time, and it’s like this data is not important enough to make the effort to anonymise it sufficiently to share it. By anonymising it enough to share it, you take out so much of value, it does not have, it’s not worth doing anymore.” [E_035_S]

A values-based ORD review process would allow researchers to query the availability, nature, quality and interpretability of potential research data outputs, and to assess the value of specific proposed ORD activities and outputs. Values-based ORD review would support consideration of a range of concerns, primarily the work and costs involved in preparation, curation, storage/ open publication, the sustainability of ORD, including in relation to the environmental impacts of long-term repository storage, the existence, or not, of relevant audiences, the likelihood of greater scrutiny or reuse and the need to prioritise other competing research outputs. Currently ORD policy and guidance (and also the Concordat on ORD) typically refers explicitly to the need for consideration of ethical concerns related to the identification of personal human data, and commercial interests. These narrower considerations are relevant to a decision to the closed vs. openly published storage of research data. Policy and guidance is silent on the consideration of more fundamental questions of purpose, impact and value in the creation of ORD. It refers instead to overarching purposes and values, such as ‘transparency and open communication’ as a founding principle of the UK Research Integrity Concordat, or making publicly funded research publicly available, that are relevant to all funded researchers:

“The value and utility of research outputs increases the more broadly they are available to be considered and used by others, including scholars, businesses and charities around the globe, as well as society in general. Access for everyone in any location to [this university’s] preserved and shared research data will also help to highlight the excellence of its research. It will attract scholars and students, foster collaboration, and enhance public engagement with research, and maximise the intellectual, social, cultural and economic impact of research.”
[Research Data Management Policy, University of Oxford, available on the Research Data Oxford website]

Structured, formal or simply recommended processes for consideration of ORD quality, costs, benefits and value, in relation to proposed outputs, uses, and impacts, are not clearly set out in institutional policy, guidance or ethical review procedures. Yet, giving space to careful consideration of the purpose, quality and value of ORD activities and outputs at the time of project development, would require researchers to: i) set out the time/work and costs needed to prepare and publish ORD; ii) outline plausible and/or intended impacts and ways these might be strengthened; iii) increase the acceptability of ORD practices through recognition of the benefits, impacts, and value in relation to costs, and by supporting exemption in cases where costs outweigh benefits. Creating space within project development, oversight and governance procedures to consider the merits (or otherwise) of proposed ORD activities, may be especially useful for researchers who are unfamiliar with publishing ORD, or are questioning the value of proposed ORD outputs.

Preliminary ORD review processes, that include consideration of the purpose, quality and value of proposed ORD outputs, and the different costs and risks inherent in open and closed approaches, are not evident in research project development and oversight procedures (e.g. research ethics review, data management plans). Better formulated processes and guidance for preliminary ORD review would help researchers to consider the purpose and value of proposed ORD activities and outputs, in relation to other research concerns. This would support better formulated ORD workplans and better justified ORD costs and could help researchers to recognise the worth in their ORD activities, and ways to increase the chances of impact.

A more inclusive version of ORD implementation could formalise due consideration of the value of ORD for diverse research projects. This could be part of formal ethical review or project management oversight, and would ensure that researchers appropriately consider the relevance and value of potential ORD outputs before deciding what kinds of resources to commit to this work. Formal ORD review process could include considerations of the value of potentially available ORD outputs relative to:

- ontological and epistemological basis of the research;
- specific research questions, objectives, practices and outputs;
- likely costs (time/cost) of ORD preparation and storage;
- likely impact on quality through, for example, greater scrutiny;
- likelihood of uptake by relevant audiences;
- likelihood of reuse;
- interests and concerns of relevant research communities;
- potential contribution to institutional knowledge exchange goals;
- environmental impacts of long-term repository storage/open publication;

- impact on other research priorities

Formal ORD review processes would need to be informed by common and accepted standards and expectations developed by research communities and other stakeholders based, where possible, on evidence.

Formal ORD review processes could usefully underpin ORD budgets, which might be higher where ORD is deemed an important and valuable but costly output. Conversely, formal exemptions could be granted, allowing researchers to entirely avoid ORD work and requirements in cases where the preservation of ORD is insufficiently justified.

There is a danger here, if institutional ORD requirements are activated, without first ensuring processes for consideration of ORD value and justification of ORD exemption. The risk is that ORD activities will be undertaken, regardless of cost or value, to satisfy extrinsic requirements, resulting in superficial, wasteful and bureaucratic ORD activities. In the context of tight financial constraints, with multiple pressures on funders, institutions, departments and researchers, top-down requirements to pursue unjustified ORD activities, would be frustrating for researchers and liable to devalue and undermine support for ORD practices. However, there is another danger, following from this situation, which is that researchers and institutions could have a strong interest in reducing work and costs by avoiding ORD activities. Clear frameworks and accountable processes will be needed to manage any perceived conflicts of interest. Nevertheless, somewhat paradoxically, lessening the ubiquity of requirements for ORD activities, by strapping commitments to ORD outputs to a preliminary review of their value and purpose and allowing justified exemptions, may ultimately encourage more ubiquitous commitment to ORD activities.

Formal processes of preliminary ORD review could help researchers to consider the potential contribution of their ORD outputs in relation to tangible ORD goals and mechanisms for data uptake and reuse. For instance, if the goals of ORD are to increase transparency, reuse and knowledge exchange: Which people, communities or organisations would most benefit from access to the ORD outputs? Are these speculative or plausible, or already identified entities? Are they ready and waiting to receive the data? How will they find out about this specific dataset? How easy will it be for them to access and reuse the data? Will they need specialist support and if so, is this readily available? Explicitly connecting potential ORD outputs, uses and impacts, could help researchers identify key audiences and engage in appropriate FAIR data curation, publication, promotion and skills sharing activities, supporting greater ease of access and likelihood of effective reuse. Critical review of the value of proposed ORD outputs and uses could help researchers to avoid wasteful ORD activities and also to make manifest the benefits, where ORD outputs hold value to others and, through reuse, to our collective knowledge, wisdom, development and advance.

6.3.6 The need to attend to gaps in engagement work to ensure inclusivity in processes of ORD implementation and oversight

“It’s a disciplinary culture – that some disciplines are signed on. I don’t think it’s an accident that [PVC for Research] came from Psychology.”

[C_009_S_FG1]

Descriptions of institutional ORD ‘research community engagement’, typically involved researchers who were familiar with ORD practices and had discipline-based (endogenously-driven) interests in ORD practices (e.g. experimental psychologists, concerned about the ‘reproducibility crisis’ within their own discipline). Conversely, researchers in disciplines which were relatively disengaged from ORD activities and concerns, were less likely to be taking

part in institutional ORD implementation work (e.g. policy, strategy and infrastructure development or oversight committees).

“We’ve got representation [on our Open Data Working Group]... one academic representative. Ideally, we’d like more, but it’s quite difficult to persuade academics to join – and find academics who’ve got... sufficient interest in the research... for people to think conceptually about particular forms of academic work being research – or be part of the ethic system – or being data – and the wide definitions of the term – is quite conceptually alienating.” [O_025_M_DEC]

This engagement bias raises concerns about systematic gaps in the kinds of research community experiences and interests that are driving and shaping institutional ORD implementation and oversight. As ORD oversight processes are developed, standards of practice, evaluation and reward systems will need to be linked to specific ORD performance indicators. For instance, if researchers who are currently disengaged from ORD activities do not become part of the processes that are shaping ORD requirements and oversight, the indicators selected for ORD assessment may be increasingly liable to bias. The outputs of some over other research communities may be better defined and captured and in this way favoured. Researchers in disciplines with less favoured ORD outputs will be at risk of losing prestige, funding, status and/or institutional support.

Engaging more diverse communities of researchers in ORD oversight and management would allow researchers with varied perspectives on value and/or more unusual ORD outputs, to ensure these are recognised and that ORD implementation is fair. Diverse researchers, including those who are currently disengaged from ORD practices, may be vital to establishing fair processes of exemption from ORD practices.

However, researchers who are currently disengaged from ORD practices, will first need to be persuaded that engagement in institutional ORD governance, implementation and review processes might be in the specific interests of those who do not see the relevance of ORD to their work.

Current engagement with research communities to support ORD implementation and oversight, appears to be insufficiently inclusive. New approaches may be needed to bring a broader range of research community members to the work of ORD oversight, implementation and evaluation. It is especially important that those who do not automatically see the relevance of ORD to their work are able to contribute to the development of ORD governance and exemption procedures.

If researchers who are disengaged from ORD practices do not engage in ORD implementation and oversight processes, and do not create appropriate exemption or assessment criteria, whole areas of research could be unfairly devalued by standards of practice and measures of ORD performance that do not evenly serve disciplinarily diverse research communities.

Alongside ensuring greater inclusivity in researcher engagement, the development of UKHEI ORD policy and guidance would benefit from: i) stronger recognition of variability in the relevance of research outputs to ORD goals; ii) establishing formalised processes of ORD review.

Current ORD review processes may need to broaden their remit, to fully recognise the variability of research outputs, and better support researchers, institutions and funders to check the relevance of ORD activities to the goals of both research and the overarching ORD agenda. Formal processes of ORD review would strengthen ORD planning, the justification of ORD costs and, where appropriate, allow ORD exemption. This would avoid institutions and funders unfairly penalising research which does not lend itself to ORD activities and where ORD activities are not sufficiently justified in relation to research and/or ORD goals.

6.3.7 The need to attend to recognition and reward for ORD practices

“... we have ... a newly created open research working group, which, one of the things that they’re keen to do is to try and build in [a] sort of reward for open research practices ... as well as to ... build it into hiring criteria, that kind of stuff, when applicable because obviously it’s not always applicable... this working group [is] interested in trying to achieve that as an incentive reward structure.” [W_038_S_B]

As outlined, for researchers in disciplines with advanced ORD practices, there are intrinsic rewards for ORD activities; with tangible gains in efficiency, collaboration, knowledge advance, public recognition and acquisition of funds. For others, in research areas where reuse of ORD is not yet commonplace, ORD activities may be poorly recognised and intrinsic rewards lacking. For researchers engaging in ORD activities in areas of research where ORD is not a fully activated concern, external recognition and reward could bolster emerging efforts, boosting the profile of researchers, bringing attention to, and encouraging others to engage in, ORD activities.

“There’s no actual recognition for the amount of open data you’ve got put up into the repository each year. There’s not like a celebration of those who have produced loads of data in the year and got that data in the repository.” [N_031_S]

However, recognition of ORD practices, is not yet baked into institutional processes of evaluation, recognition or reward for research workers. Systematic monitoring and evaluation of researchers’ ORD activities is not yet integrated within wider departmental and institutional oversight processes. Most institutions were awaiting UKRI/REF guidance before further developing their ORD policies, standards and compliance procedures. ORD workers meantime described a range of laborious efforts to capture researchers’ ORD activities and numerous challenges to making these processes more systematic. Nevertheless, ORD workers were readily able to pick out and identify ORD success stories, often as a result of their direct involvement in supporting, or collecting evidence to demonstrate researchers’ ORD activities. However, this awareness of researchers’ ORD activities, did not directly relate to any formal institutional recognition or reward for ORD activities.

“...there was a bit of work ... around ‘Rewards and Recognition for Open Practices’ – and maybe having prizes and things like that. We have no

remit to run anything like that...we've got no ability to push it forward – and no ability to resource it.” [A_001_S]

Some ORD workers described 'open research weeks' or 'ORD weeks' that showcased diverse research community ORD outputs and/or small prizes for excellence in ORD. However, it was unclear how widely those outside of ORD teams attend these events or recognise institutional ORD success stories. ORD prizes and annual ORD showcasing events appeared to be relatively new attempts to bring attention to ORD activities. It was unclear if these awards or showcasing events are already widely recognised, whether they have reached the attention of departmental leads, and to what extent they are raising the profile of, or encouraging wider interest in, ORD activities.

Some institutions have introduced ORD Champions or Data Champion programs. In this case, alongside recognising an individual's exemplary ORD practices, achievements or expertise, the 'Data Champion' takes on responsibilities to support wider ORD activities. ORD champions commit to contributing to departmental and/or institutional ORD activities, such as by attending relevant meetings, sharing ORD skills, encouraging engagement in ORD practices among peers and generally supporting ORD implementation within their department or research group. However, the ORD Champion role was sometimes viewed with scepticism. In smaller institutions, constrained financial circumstances can lead researchers to take on multiple institutional roles and responsibilities, creating heavy workloads. In this context, there was concern an accolade that placed additional responsibilities on high performing, but already overburdened, researchers, would be seen as a poisoned chalice and would be shunned.

A limited array of prizes have been awarded beyond institutions, by high profile funders, to recognise and reward achievements in open research data. UKRI awards in this area are currently under review but included an 'Open Science Impact Prize' that included a substantial award (£20,000), paid to the host institution, to support the awardee(s) to engage in additional open research activities, in recognition of the strength of prior work in this area. The GW4 Alliance awards a £250 'Open Research Prize' recognising excellence in open research data practices among GW4 funded projects, and is presented as part of Open Research Week, which showcases ORD practices among GW4 research projects.

This contrasts with the level of formal and informal reward and recognition associated with peer-reviewed journal publications (with prizes and rewards routinely offered by journals, institutions, departments). As one ORD worker explained:

“But the hurdle you've still got to get over [to better recognise ORD publication] is one of kudos. ...we have a school in the university ...that rewards academics over £2,000 for each article they publish in a highly cited journal...So that's a direct financial incentive. You know, everything is geared towards this.... we have to start deciding what we value.”
[W_038_S_D]

All in all, recognition and reward that might encourage burgeoning ORD activities, especially in fields where intrinsic recognition and reward for ORD activities remains limited, was patchy – evident, but not yet extensively, and in the case of institutional prizes, these were mostly small. A number of institutions ran open data showcasing events, and more substantial prizes have been awarded by large funders. On the whole, institutional prizes that might bring recognition and prestige to ORD activities are increasingly prevalent but neither widespread nor high profile.

6.3.8 The need to attend to ORD performance and career progression

Another pathway to meaningful recognition and reward for ORD activities and achievements, is via career progression and recruitment criteria.

“as a university that whole sort of promotion, recognition side of things I don’t really feel that we’ve been able to implement that.” [G_010_S]

A few institutions had updated promotion criteria to explicitly recognise and reward ORD activities and achievements, but most had not. Mostly, it was unclear that the work and achievements of ORD creation, curation, or reuse, would directly benefit career progression (e.g. recruitment or promotion).

6.3.9 The need to attend to recognition and reward for ORD reuse

For many research communities and disciplines, searching ORD databases to access and make use of ORD made available by others within their research community, is not yet part of established routine research practice. Unlike processes of review (of relevant published work) or the use of openly available administrative data, the identification (searching national and international ORD databases) and reuse (e.g. descriptions, summaries, analysis) of relevant open research data is only rarely the focus of research applications, or included within the preliminary stages of project development work.

There are a small number of funding opportunities that specifically support projects that focus on ORD reuse (e.g. ESRC Responsive mode: Secondary data analysis grants, Wellcome Open Research Fund, ADR UK Research Fellowships). However, these remain few. In general, funding awards across disciplines, while routinely requiring ORD outputs, are much more likely to stipulate that research projects undertake preliminary systematic review work (appraisal of available research publications), than ORD database searches and ORD reuse.

Similarly, published research demonstrating the systematic use of ORD database searches (documenting relevant search procedures and databases) and appropriate methods of analysis, or models for combining or summarising relevant ORD, are not yet prevalent across disciplines. Funding awards that stipulate or encourage ORD reuse, as part of broader projects (e.g. UKRI Future Leaders Fellowship), could help shift research communities towards greater ORD reuse, and strengthen journal publication in this area. Published work demonstrating standards of excellence in ORD reuse methodologies, of relevance to diverse research communities, would be a useful spur and guide researchers in successful approaches to ORD reuse.

6.3.10 The need to attend to the invisibility of ORD labour

Where researchers undertake, or intend to undertake, ORD activities, the time and labour involved is unlikely to have been accurately accounted for in project management planning, costed into project activities, or recognised as part of research workload. Consequently, in many disciplines, workload pressures and resource constraints, alongside the normal pressures of research cultures (e.g. short term research contracts, producing peer review publications, applications for work or funding) may leave little space for exemplary ORD practices.

Partly through unfamiliarity with the demands of data curation and repository functionality, and partly through inadequate incorporation of ORD activities within project plans, researchers are liable to underestimate the time and work involved in preparing and publishing ORD in an appropriate repository to FAIR standards (FAIR standards are referenced in most university ORD policy, statements, guidance and/or training). Researcher unfamiliarity places a burden on both researchers and ORD workers, who often provide detailed support to researchers seeking to upload data to a university ORD repository. ORD workers provide extensive support partly to skill share, hoping to build expertise within research communities, and partly to ensure repository data curation standards are maintained, so that datasets are sufficiently findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable (FAIR).

“...I’m trying to embrace FAIR principles and because this is so time consuming... what I do is somebody uploads a dataset into Pure, I schedule a one-to-one with a researcher and I’ll say to them, look, can we look at your file naming convention? ...Can we look at the abstract? Can we look at the WH interrogatives? Who? Why? What? Where? All of those things, what is this about? Explain it to me. Here’s your institutional README file, you need to complete this, you need a code book. Sometimes I’ll go through, if I have time, if it’s a spreadsheet and a tabular data, I’ll say, okay, sorry, you’ve got values there that relate in cell three, 235, 35, out of what? What does that mean? Very often researchers will know the data so well, but think their data is shareable and usable, and because I don’t have any knowledge of their data it’s actually ideal, because I’ll say I don’t understand what that means, can you tell me? Then they’ll say, ‘oh, I might need to put this down in a document’... That is very labour intensive to do and very often, when you’ve had the one to one with the researcher, you feel energised, but often they don’t actually follow that up by implementing the changes, so you have to chase them up, so you have to constantly set reminders.” [X_039_S_b]

ORD labour that is not properly accounted for in project planning (workplans, budgets and funding applications) easily becomes “invisible work”, placing pressure on researchers to perform time-consuming tasks to high standards, in tight time frames, and likely reducing the quality of squeezed ORD practices. There are also well-known EDI concerns with respect to who often does “invisible work”.

One ORD worker suggested that researchers should allow approximately three months dedicated curation time to properly prepare data for publication in formats that are FAIR (findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable). However, if research funding is for a relatively short 6-12 month project, 3 months-worth of dedicated ORD activities would significantly extend the funding period, or curtail aspects of the planned research project. Unless funders have made clear an expectation to see significant weight given to time and costs for ORD activities, it is highly likely that these will be under-estimated, and that over the course of the project other research pressures will further limit opportunities to take on ORD activities.

ORD workers described two periods when researchers were most likely to engage with research data teams: i) at the application stage, if detailed data management plans are required as part of project proposals/applications to funders; ii) at the end of the project when an open access journal stipulates that data related to a paper must be available in an openly available format, before the paper can be published. Both are likely moments of time-constrained pressure, again limiting attention to ORD practices and skills development. Without data specialists stepping in to perform detailed final checks on datasets, it seems likely that ORD data preparation and curation, left in the hands of harried researchers, may fall short of FAIR standards.

Another dominant research culture threat to ORD, is that researchers with the closest knowledge of project data are often working on short-term contracts. The risk is that contracts may end before the completion of intended ORD activities, and that important information will be lost to the dataset, reducing the chance of effective ORD curation. The uncosted, unaccounted for invisibility of ORD labour increases this risk.

Throughout this set of concerns, it is evident that i) researchers are mostly attending to ORD under duress, to satisfy funder or publisher stipulations, rather than in a values-driven self-directed way that would allow more time and space for skills development and thorough ORD activities; ii) the dominant research culture, focused on securing funding and peer-reviewed publications continues to prevail, and this is to the detriment of ORD practices. In these circumstances, ORD tasks create additional, invisible, workload pressures. If the purpose, impacts and value of ORD activities are not apparent, or incentivised, it will be hard for researchers to justify their time spent on ORD tasks, further undermining ORD standards.

Here again, a preliminary values-based review of proposed ORD activities, that justified exemptions, could lead to positive outcomes for researchers and for ORD. Exemption from poorly justified ORD tasks could alleviate the strain on researchers, and conversely strengthen a values-based commitment to ORD practices when justified, costed and planned. In this way a virtuous cycle flows from more stringent justification of ORD activities, increasing the chances of attentive ORD activities, and maintaining standards in ORD publication.

Incidentally, ORD workers were frustrated that major funders had removed the data management planning requirement for research proposals (to reduce time-consuming application workloads for applicants). Researchers' difficulties with completing detailed data management plans had resulted in an opportunity for contact with ORD teams, who were able to inject some practical insight and expertise into project proposals. In removing this component from applications, funders intended for them to be completed after the offer of funding. However, ORD workers said that without the pressure of funding application, this did not readily happen.

Ensuring ORD training, skills development, data preparation and curation activities are properly built into researchers' contracted work would likely preserve and protect the quality of ORD outputs.

As things stand, researchers competing for competitive funding awards, may be concerned that costing ORD practices into funding application will make their project overly expensive and jeopardise their chances of success. Funders may expect ORD activities to fall within institutional administrative budgets and view negatively additional requests for time and funds to perform ORD activities. Clarity around funder expectations in this area would also help to make ORD work a visible, costed and time-allocated aspect research project planning and delivery.

Relatedly, it is **unclear that institutional finance services or funders are yet able to accurately estimate ORD costs** both during a project and in terms of long-term archiving. Standardised costings for ORD work do not yet appear to be part of the nomenclature of institutional professional support or research communities.

7. Discussion

Despite identified areas of progression in institutional ORD, notably in relation to increasing policy and infrastructure provision and to some evident ORD practices, our analysis identified three high level categories of concerns and barriers to ORD progress, representing different kinds of underlying problems, that each require different kinds of related work, collaboration, specialist attention and action.

1) **value-based issues** - resulting from variations in direct/indirect experience and recognition of the potential use and impact of ORD within disciplinarily diverse research communities, and the need to bolster intrinsic and/or incentivised rewards;

2) **compliance issues** – the setting of ORD requirements; the associated need for systems of monitoring, audit and evaluation of ORD practices; lack of agreement on the appropriate metrics of evaluation;

3) **pragmatic/technical issues** - practical problems – relating to things that need to be bought, built, grown, nurtured, learnt, changed or developed (requiring systems and technical developments, human and other infrastructure resources, time, funds) to make institutional ORD workable and to make the whole ORD system work.

The compliance and pragmatic/technical issues have been rehearsed elsewhere (for example, European Commission (51), though not comprehensively and systematically, and this remains a gap in the literature. Our main focus in this report is on the values-based issues (Section 6.3.1), though we do briefly note the main compliance and pragmatic/technical issues that arose in the fieldwork (Sections 6.3.3 and 6.3.4).

7.1 Values-based concerns

In the drive to transform open research practices, we have been presented with a grand overarching vision for a future in which ORD is normalised, with many benefits to processes of knowledge creation, advance and access (promoting transparency, integrity, efficiency, equity). Those questioning the value of their own ORD outputs are reminded that they are contributing to a grand open data vision of tomorrow. As a consequence, ORD policy and guidance appears so far to have largely avoided more fundamental questioning of the purpose and value of particular ORD outputs, in relation to particular research endeavours and objectives, in the here and now. This means pressing pragmatic questions, relevant to the appropriate allocation of time and costs to ORD work, in the context of competing research priorities, have been largely overlooked. Policy and guidance instead refers to overarching values and purposes related to a generalised ‘grand’ vision of future ORD impacts. As the Concordat on ORD states under Principle 3 (addressing the significant costs involved in ORD activities):

“All of these costs must be balanced with the benefits to the research portfolio as a whole”

Emphasising the overall value of ORD activities makes sense, in the context of the early phase of a major effort to drive uptake and implementation of ORD practices among institutions and research communities. The outcomes, as outlined (see 6.1, above), have been positive: institutions are on board, ORD workers are in post, institutional ORD repository space is available and supported: a commitment to ORD is both stated in policy and demonstrated in infrastructure.

However, taking the next step towards implementation of fully normalised and universal open research practices may require a more mature and nuanced stance. To effectively plan our everyday work, in pressured environments, with multiple competing demands on our time and budgets, we need to be able to question the value and purpose of particular activities, in relation to the wider objectives of our research projects and the constraints we experience (time, budgets, qualified workers). The rational notion that ORD activities may vary in value, worth and impact, and consequently that some ORD activities and outputs may not be worth the effort and costs involved, is in danger of becoming an elephant in the room, that will inevitably guide pragmatic decisions, whether or not it is acknowledged.

Rather than continually emphasising ORD value in a generalised, future-oriented, sense, it may now be the right time to acknowledge that the value of ORD outputs can and will vary, and that as a consequence, in the context of very real constraints on time and funds, ORD activities will not always be justified, and will not always be warranted. This simple acknowledgement, opens the door to proper consideration of the purpose, quality and value of specific ORD outputs, and importantly, to occasional exemptions from ORD activities, where these are not clearly justified. Many practical beneficial consequences flow from an approach to ORD that allows for a preliminary consideration and specification of the value, purpose, benefit and justification of costs related to ORD activities.

Reinforcing connection to the value and impact of ORD activities

Counter-intuitively, loosening the universality of ORD requirements, and requiring tighter justification for specific ORD activities, may ease and steady the process towards more widespread ORD activities, and more normalised uptake. If researchers are encouraged to engage in ORD activities only when the work and costs involved have been considered in relation to the perceived benefits and impacts of ORD outputs, they will be asked to commit only to justified, meaningful, ORD activities. Since the work and costs involved in ORD activities may be extensive, involving training and skills development and detailed curation work, this justification and clarity of purpose is important. Researchers and research teams with pressured workloads will be better able to allocate the necessary time to ORD activities, where there is a strong, values-driven, purpose, that has been transparently considered in relation to other research priorities. This better supports the allocation of time, where needed, to ORD skills development. At the same time avoiding wasteful, costly, and burdensome, ORD activities reduces undermining workload pressures, for research teams, researchers and for ORD workers. This eases tensions in the relationships between institutional policy and oversight, and interests and priorities of professional service and research communities. This opens a virtuous cycle, where the overarching values of ORD activities are strengthened and preserved; valuable and impactful ORD is published and reused, and the tangible benefits of ORD practices drive further and more widespread values-based ORD activity.

7.2 Compliance issues

As noted above, the STAR Report has focused strongly on values-based barriers. What follows in this and the subsequent section therefore is only a high level summary of the findings with respect to compliance and pragmatic/technical issues.

- a) Policies often state expectations, but do not specify compliance mechanisms. Many institutions and other organisations such as funders have high-level ORD policy statements, but these often lack detail on:
 - How compliance will be checked
 - Who is responsible for monitoring
 - What counts as compliance
 - What happens when researchers do not comply

Policies frequently promote the value of ORD, but do not include clear implementation plans or enforcement structures. Some policies imply requirements (e.g., “researchers should make data open”) but these are not backed by monitoring systems, leading to a gap between stated expectations and actual practice.

- b) Monitoring and evaluation processes are underdeveloped or missing. Monitoring of ORD practices is weak, inconsistent, or absent. Institutions do not have clear metrics or methods for tracking ORD publication, tracking reuse, assessing impact or evaluating adherence to ORD policy. Monitoring is typically described as manual, labour-intensive, difficult to scale and not systematically embedded in institutional processes. ORD specialists often rely on informal awareness of who is publishing data, rather than structured reporting systems.
- c) Compliance with funder requirements is uncertain and rarely checked. Participants report that ORD commitments made in funding bids (e.g., in data management plans) are not routinely followed up by funders. There is little evidence that institutions systematically check whether researchers deliver the ORD outputs promised in grant applications or meet funder mandated data sharing requirements. As a result, it is unclear that ORD commitments, typically those that are required in funding bids as part of data management plans, are routinely achieved.
- d) Compliance depends heavily on journals, not institutions. Researchers often publish data only when required by journals, not because of institutional or funder policy or monitoring. This means compliance is externalised, with journals acting as the de facto compliance mechanism. Institutional policies have limited influence without external enforcement
- e) Compliance systems are constrained by limited staff capacity. ORD support teams are typically small and overstretched, often consisting of a single specialist. Because ORD support is so labour intensive, scaling up monitoring is currently impossible. Without more staff or automation, institutions cannot meaningfully monitor compliance.
- f) Institutions are hesitant to expand compliance systems without external pressure. Many institutions are waiting for REF or UKRI to introduce stronger ORD requirements before investing in monitoring systems, compliance processes or evaluation frameworks. This creates a policy vacuum wherein institutions support ORD in principle but avoid building compliance infrastructure until required to do so.
- g) Lack of agreed metrics makes compliance evaluation difficult. Participants reported that there appears to be no consensus on what counts as a “good” ORD output, how to measure FAIRness or reuse, and how to evaluate impact. Without agreed, shared metrics, institutions cannot compare performance, benchmark progress or consistently report compliance.

In summary, compliance challenges are recognised as a major barrier to ORD progress. Participants identify compliance issues as one of the three major categories of barriers to ORD progress. The oversight and governance of ORD requirements is unclear, monitoring, audit, and evaluation systems are underdeveloped, metrics for evaluation are lacking. These gaps are seen as sector wide problems, not just institutional ones.

7.3 Pragmatic/technical issues

Participants reported a range of practical problems relating to things that need to be bought, built, grown, nurtured, learnt, changed or developed (requiring systems and technical developments, human and other infrastructure resources, time, funds) to make institutional ORD workable and to make the whole ORD system work.

- a) In terms of staffing, ORD specialists exist, but teams are very small. Most institutions have one ORD specialist or a very small team. Smaller HEIs often rely on one part-time or partial-role worker, who may also handle bibliometrics, repository management, or other duties. Larger institutions may have a few specialists, but even these teams are stretched. ORD support roles are therefore overburdened, providing as they do policy drafting, training data management planning support, metadata checking, repository intake and DOI minting and one-to-one data curation support. This level of personalised support is not scalable if ORD becomes routine. Institutions typically do not have discipline-specific data stewards who understand local research practices. This leaves ORD specialists isolated from disciplinary contexts and unable to distribute workload. ORD staff feel isolated within the institution and with limited institutional leverage; they often feel they must “wave the risk flag” to get senior attention. They typically lack authority to influence institutional decisions or secure resources.
- b) Researchers’ data skills are limited. Many researchers lack skills, understanding and literacy in data curation, metadata, FAIR principles and repository requirements. ORD specialists spend significant time explaining basics like file naming, README files, codebooks, and variable definitions. Training uptake is uneven; postgraduates often complete mandatory training but senior researchers and supervisors rarely attend voluntary sessions. This creates a skills gap and increases reliance on ORD specialists.
- c) ORD work is often hidden, ‘invisible labour’. It is rarely costed or planned in research projects and, even when it is, researchers underestimate the time needed for FAIR compliant data preparation. Furthermore, short term contracts mean key data knowledge may be lost before curation is complete.
- d) Data curation implies work for ORD specialists to review metadata, check file naming conventions, ensure documentation is complete and identify missing contextual information. It is labour-intensive. Researchers often do not follow up on requested changes, requiring repeated reminders. The FAIR principles are widely referenced but hard to implement. FAIR is embedded in guidance, but researchers struggle to interpret FAIR in practice and metadata quality varies widely. ORD specialists must intervene heavily to maintain standards or risk poor quality ORD outputs that are uninterpretable, poorly documented and not reusable.
- e) Repositories exist, but capacity is limited. Most institutions have a repository (Pure, Figshare, bespoke systems) but many repositories are described as “repositories of last resort”, that is, they are intended for data that cannot go to a disciplinary repository and are not always the best fit for visibility or reuse. Participants noted concerns with respect to storage capacity. Current usage is low enough that capacity

is not yet a crisis but institutions anticipate storage limits and rising costs. Indeed, some institutions already impose soft restrictions on very large datasets. There is a need for more scalable infrastructure. Institutions encourage use of discipline specific repositories, but participants noted that not all disciplines have them, researchers often don't know how to find or use them, and they may vary in quality and sustainability. Repository upgrades require major effort, for example migrating data to new systems is time consuming and technically complex. ORD specialists often lead procurement and migration with limited support. Some participants noted a future comprising metadata-only institutional repositories, which link to externally hosted data, reducing storage burden. However, this requires better interoperability and consistent metadata standards.

- f) In terms of financial and resourcing issues, ORD costs are poorly understood and rarely budgeted. Researchers often underestimate curation time, fail to cost storage and avoid including ORD costs in grant applications. Finance teams lack standardised costing models for ORD. Furthermore, institutional financial pressures threaten ORD progress, since many HEIs face budget cuts, staffing freezes and uncertainty about future funding. ORD is vulnerable because it is not yet embedded. The benefits are long term and diffuse, while it competes with more immediate priorities. Repository storage costs are a growing concern because long term preservation is expensive. Institutions therefore worry about sustainability, and also the environmental impact of data storage. It remains unclear who pays for ongoing storage after a project ends, which means that ORD support roles are not secure; many ORD workers are on fixed term or precarious contracts and institutions hesitate to expand teams without external mandates (e.g., REF requirements).
- g) There are systemic operational challenges. ORD processes are not yet integrated into institutional workflows; ORD is often bolted on at the end of projects. As noted above, there is no systematic monitoring or reporting but further, there is rarely integration with ethics review or with how promotion or appraisal systems work in practice. Institutions lack tools for automated FAIR assessment and metadata extraction, and for tracking ORD outputs across systems. Requirements from journals, institutions and funders create fragmented, inconsistent and reactive workflows.

8. Recommendations

8.1 Addressing the value of open research

1. *Recognition and reward for ORD practices are lacking...*

Incentives for ORD should be embedded in institutional hiring and promotion at all levels, and in research funding and awards. Incentives should recognise not just publishing ORD, but also the use of ORD. International cooperation will be needed to ensure that researchers with global career horizons are positively advantaged by sharing and using ORD.

2. *Invisible ORD labour is neither valued nor costed ...*

Funders should explicitly expect/require costings for ORD practices and storage in proposal budgets. Standards for costing ORD practices (including curation and repository and training costs and qualified personnel) should be developed in cooperation with research communities, ORD specialists and institutional finance staff. Use of such standards should then become expected by funders, to counter the natural inclination of researchers and institutions to minimise cost in project proposals.

3. *Disciplinary and epistemic diversity is not sufficiently recognised...*

Meaningful, substantive engagement must be conducted with diverse disciplinary communities, ensuring all can contribute to evolving guidance and to incentivising openness in ways that are relevant and meaningful, rather than burdensome and bureaucratic. More inclusive examples and language is needed. Future requirements for ORD (e.g. REF) also need to be inclusive, so they appropriately engage and do not count against, or create meaningless bureaucracy, for whole research communities.

4. *The reuse of ORD is not normative...*

Training/advocacy for ORD practices should highlight examples of the use of published data. Research reviews/assessments should include ORD sharing and reuse, using discipline-relevant quality standards. Just as funders expect proposals to position potential projects in the literature landscape, so they should also expect to see potential projects positioned with respect to existing data sources. Excellence in data re-use (for scrutiny, or to inform future research) should be rewarded using existing mechanisms.

5. *Inadequate evaluation of quality and sustainability of ORD...*

Disciplinary communities and institutions need to develop and enact collaborative processes for evaluating the nature and quality of data that is appropriate to be made open, in preparation for sharing. Such evaluation needs to include balancing competing ethical concerns, for instance: the potential future worth of stored open research data; the resources required for curation and long-term preservation; sustainability and environmental impacts; participant engagement in the terms of reuse and generated outputs; ORD audiences and issues of access; as well as on-going concerns related to the safety and anonymity of protected participant data; the potential use of open research data in controversial ways that were not as initially intended, including, as AI models increasingly take hold, various forms of

algorithmically-generated, information-assimilating, machine learning derived, computerised outputs.

8.2 Addressing compliance issues

6. *Under-developed monitoring and reporting of ORD practices...*

Systematic overarching monitoring strategies should be developed and tested. Measures for monitoring institutional and research community ORD practices need to be built on meaningful engagement with diverse disciplines and with wider stakeholders, to support coherent, inclusive approaches. The monitoring burden should be shared among stakeholders, including funders, digital technology and repository providers, publishers and institutions. Coordination mechanisms will be needed to achieve this.

7. *Compliance-driven commitments with uncertain delivery...*

ORD commitments (as part of funding applications, or data management plans) need to be reviewed throughout projects, by project teams and institutions, but also through funder audits, to support delivery/compliance. Methods for checking compliance (as with monitoring in general) should be discipline appropriate.

8.3 Addressing pragmatic concerns:

8. *ORD support capacity is limited...*

Changes to ORD expectations and requirements that impact entire research communities need to be gradual, to correspond with the development of scalable support mechanisms, as described in other recommendations.

9. *Institutional repositories have limited capacity...*

Where needed, external (non-institutional) and discipline-appropriate ORD repositories should be developed, with accessible training and support to ensure that these are trustworthy, sustained, accessible and signalled to researchers and that data is appropriately curated. Costs for data repositories should be shared among stakeholders, i.e. not just universities but also funders. Agreements will need to be made about the principles on which this cost distribution is based.

10. *Data stewardship roles are lacking...*

Funders and institutions should continue to research and mature the concept of “data stewards” with clear roles and responsibilities, and develop funding mechanisms for them to be long-term positions in universities. Existing projects, for example in the UKRI Digital Research Infrastructure programme, could provide a sound basis for this work. Embedded (and, where relevant, workloaded) data stewards are a key mechanism whereby ORD remains a matter for research communities, basing ORD on nuanced understandings of practice rather than it being a matter purely of compliance with extrinsic requirements.

11. *ORD support roles are isolated...*

Data specialists should be represented in institutional decision-making bodies, such as – but not limited to – research committees. ORD specialists may benefit from strengthened peer networking opportunities, including in person (rather than email list) contact with those in equivalent roles in other diverse institutions, which could

potentially also support the sharing of emerging good practices. Institutions should ensure that ORD specialists, finance, commercialisation and other professionals are better connected internally. This will enable better ORD workflows and, furthermore, enable institutions to engage more effectively with external stakeholders such as funders and system providers.

12. Financial climate may threaten ORD practices...

Institutions should inventory resources/infrastructures for ORD that are dependent on institution versus external funding, and ring-fence appropriate funding to protect valued ORD provisions. Work focused on strengthening the connection between underpinning values and related ORD requirements, could help to defend ORD practices in the face of on-going and anticipated sector-wide financial cuts and constraints. Funders should be mindful that reductions in budgets and bureaucracy may be achieved at the cost of impacts to their other strategic aims, such as the growth of ORD.

8.4 Concluding recommendation

13. Institutional review

Institutions should establish formalised institutional or departmental processes of ORD review, at the relevant point prior to research starting. The review could be implemented as an addition to current ethical review processes or as part of data management planning or, ideally, as a combined and integrated review. Formal ORD review processes would allow researchers to strengthen and better formulate their ORD outputs, by setting out and justifying the time, skilled labour and costs involved in generating ORD outputs, and any additional work required to connect proposed ORD outputs to relevant audiences beyond their proximate research community, and to increase opportunities for anticipated scrutiny and impact. This process of review would allow projects to better specify, justify and account for ORD costs in their project budgets, removing the invisibility of ORD labour and better connecting research communities to the inherent value of ORD outputs in relation to their own work. This would also allow projects where justification for ORD outputs remained weak, and other research priorities and impacts were better supported, to avoid ORD work, costs and outputs, through formal exemption, allowing research time, costs and efforts to be focused more appropriately on other areas. The review processes should apply to all research, including doctoral research; in those cases close involvement of supervisor(s) would be essential. We acknowledge that substantive preparatory work will be needed to ensure the proposed review processes are efficient, balanced, well-informed and accountable, and that this work is best done at the levels of the sector and of disciplinary communities.

Glossary: STAR study definitions

ADR-UK

ADR UK — Administrative Data Research UK — is a UK-wide partnership that links and opens up de-identified public sector administrative data for accredited researchers, enabling high-quality evidence to inform policy and improve lives. It brings together government and academic partners, coordinated by a Strategic Hub within UKRI's ESRC.

AI

Artificial Intelligence; in this report generally referring to generative AI and large language models.

GW4 Alliance

The GW4 Alliance is a partnership of four research-intensive UK universities: Bath, Bristol, Cardiff and Exeter. Founded in 2013, it accelerates collaborative research, innovation and regional economic growth by combining complementary expertise, infrastructure and talent across the South West of England and South Wales

Jisc

Jisc is the UK's not-for-profit digital, data and technology agency for higher and further education, providing national infrastructure, cybersecurity, and sector-wide digital services. It operates the Janet Network, the UK's research and education network used by over 20 million people daily, and supports institutions with tools, expertise and innovation to enhance teaching, research and operations.

ORD / Open / transparent data

As defined by the Concordat on ORD, open research data are: "those research data that can be freely accessed, used, modified, and shared, provided that there is appropriate acknowledgement if required." In the context of open research used in this study, data should be as open as possible, while as closed as necessary. It should generally be transparent, even if it cannot be wholly open. That is, it should be 'FAIR – Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable'(22).

STAR

The UKRN STAR - Sustainable & TrAnsparent Research Data - project aimed to support the development by institutions of sustainable arrangements for open and transparent research data. It achieved this by engaging a diverse range of institutions in the project.

Sustainable arrangements

An inclusive phrase relating to implementation of the Concordat on ORD, that may incorporate technology, policy, procedures, skills, norms, incentives, funding, and so on, that allows the implementation to continue over the long term.

UKHEI

UK Higher Education Institution.

UKRI

UKRI — UK Research and Innovation — is the UK's national funding agency for research and innovation, bringing together the seven Research Councils, Innovate UK and Research England into a single organisation. Established in 2018, it invests public funding to advance knowledge, support innovation, and strengthen the UK's economic, societal and cultural wellbeing.

UKRN

The UKRN — UK Reproducibility Network — is a national, peer-led consortium working to improve the rigour, transparency, and reproducibility of UK research. It brings together researchers, institutions, funders and other stakeholders to coordinate training, share best practice, and strengthen research culture across disciplines.

UNESCO

The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization is a UN specialized agency that promotes global cooperation in education, science, culture, and communication.

It works with 194 member states to strengthen peace, safeguard heritage, and support sustainable development.

UUK

UUK — Universities UK — is the collective voice of the UK's universities, representing 142 vice-chancellors and principals across England, Scotland, Wales and Northern Ireland. It works to influence policy, champion the value of higher education, and support universities in delivering research, teaching and societal impact.

Wellcome

Wellcome — formally the Wellcome Trust — is a global charitable foundation established in 1936 to support science and research that improve health. It funds discovery research and major programmes in infectious disease, mental health, and climate and health, backed by one of the world's largest philanthropic endowments.

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<https://blog.westminster.ac.uk/enact/>

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